

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

D6.12: Report on dissemination and training activities no 2

WP6 - Communication, dissemination, and exploitation

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Executive summary

The present document provides an overview of the dissemination and training activities organised and/or undertaken by the NextFOOD consortium partners between 1st May 2020 and 30th April 2022. It begins with a presentation of the reporting process followed by partners. The synergies built with other projects are discussed next. Then, dissemination activities that took place during the reporting period are listed. Finally, additional information to activities pertaining to the previous reporting period (1st May 2018 – 30th April 2020) are provided, and all activities undertaken throughout the project’s lifetime (1st May 2018 – 30th April 2022) are presented by year.

1 Reporting process

In line with D6.1 “Dissemination, exploitation and outreach plan”, consortium partners were encouraged to report the results of each dissemination/training activity after these took place, listing the **specific key outcomes** of each event. Such events may have included synergies with similar projects, networking events, workshops, conferences, seminars, courses, food festivals, professional’s associations events, farmers and/or producer’s events etc. The abovementioned events were important in **disseminating the results** of the project to practitioners, **enhancing participation to the project platform** ([NextFOOD Educational Platform](#)), and **expanding the network of interest**.

All partners were asked to provide specific information about the dissemination & training activities in which they participated through a template presented in ANNEX 8 ([D6.1](#)). The event reporting template provides a summary of the whole event that pulls out the most relevant information (i.e., type, place, event aim & purpose, geographical scope, goal of presence, feedback from audience, etc; [Reporting Template](#)).

The event reporting template was filled out by partners for the below-listed activities (physical, virtual, or hybrid):

- Organization of NextFOOD conferences
- Consortium (partners) conferences
- Work Package (WP) partners’ meetings
- Organization of a workshop/seminar/networking event
- Participating/presenting on international/national conference
- Participating in workshop /seminar / networking event
- The partners shared relevant photos, videos, links.

Field	Input
Event title	Please write down the title of the event
Type	Please Choose: workshop/seminar/networking event/conference/ workshop meeting Please Clarify: Participation or Organization
Place	City, Country
Dates	DD/MM/YY
Event aim & purpose	In 150 characters please identify the objective of the event
Relevance to the project	In 150 characters please identify what is the impact of the event to the project
Type of audience	Please describe the audience attending the event and connection with targeted audience
Estimated size of targeted audience	Please provide estimation in number
Geographical scope of event	Please clarify if local/regional/national/international
Partner(s) involved	Please write down the name(s) of the partner(s)
Goal of presence	Please explain why you attended the event
Feedback from the audience	Please provide any feedback that you might have had
Stakeholders engaged	Please provide a link to the publication
	Provide any photos, video links

Partners' events reports were documented in [D6.6](#), D6.12, and in the interim reports. The contact person for the event reports was Daphne Kapsala (d.kapsala@agromacedonia.gr, Project Coordinator, ACRCM).

2 Synergies and networking with similar projects/initiatives

2.1 Overview of project synergies

Synergies with other projects that have similar scopes and objectives are an important tool for the elaboration of a project's results in new audiences and countries, and for enhancing the effectiveness of remaining project activities. To this end, consortium partners initiated and/or participated in networking and collaboration activities with 12 other projects ([Relative projects of NextFOOD](#)). These projects and related collaboration activities are briefly discussed below.

A virtual meeting with [LIAISON 2020](#) project was held on 13th February 2021, with the objective to explore opportunities for cooperation among the two Horizon projects in terms of exchanging good practices, and promoting deliverables and other outputs. The LIAISON project aims to make contributions to optimising interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of EU policies to seed up innovation in agriculture,

forestry, and rural areas. During the meeting, several points of common interest, such as common promotional tools and dissemination meetings, were identified.

The explored synergies with the [RUBIZMO](#) project were multi-level. The inception meeting took place on 16th March 2021 during which information materials were exchanged. RUBIZMO is a European initiative working to foster sustainable growth and job creation in rural areas by discovering the vital ingredients for developing entrepreneurship and successful business models in high potential sectors, such as food and agriculture, new bio-based value chains and services. The second digital meeting was held on 17th May 2021 with the participation of project managers of the [RURITAGE](#), [PoliRURAL](#), [NextFOOD](#) projects. The coordinator of [RUBIZMO](#) introduced the potential of holding a short joint virtual summer school with other EU projects focusing on rural enterprise/innovation to disseminate the training tools developed through the different projects to rural enterprise advisers, agricultural advisers, trainers, and stakeholders. Additional possibilities for collaboration relating to developed business models and to the *RUBIZMO Café Talks* that are organised each month were also explored. A third digital meeting was co-organised on 26th May 2021 for the identification of collaborative initiatives to speed up innovation in rural areas and in agri-food value chains.

The collaboration between [NEFERTITI](#) and NextFOOD was initiated during an online meeting which took place on 1st April 2021. The managers of both projects presented achieved outcomes and identified possible tools for collaboration. The overall objective of NEFERTITI is to establish an EU-wide highly connected network of demonstration and pilot farms designed to enhance knowledge exchanges, cross fertilisation among actors and efficient innovation uptake in the farming sector through peer-to-peer demonstration of techniques on 10 major agricultural challenges in Europe. They are representing a unique Network (selected for 4 years under Horizon 2020, Societal Challenge 2, RUR 12-2017 call) comprising 32 partners from 17 countries and coordinated by ACTA, the head of Network of the French Agricultural Technical Institutes.

A workshop held by the [NEWBIE network](#) and NextFOOD was conducted on 26th January 2021. NEWBIE facilitates the development and dissemination of new business models, including new entry models, to the full range of new entrants, from successors to complete newcomers, to the agricultural sector. The workshop has been followed by further collaboration relating to the dissemination of results and integration of tools and models.

Between 18 and 22 December 2020, three virtual focus group meetings were organised in the spirit of co-creation and participation by the [Med Food TTHubs](#), [InoFA](#), and NextFOOD. Med Food TTHubs aims to establish and pilot Trace & Trust Hubs focusing on Mediterranean food products, whilst InoFA represents an innovation cluster including over 40 different stakeholders across the agri-food supply chain. These events gave NextFOOD the opportunity to include a pool of recognised experts engaged in the agri-food and traceability sectors in its network. Each of the three initiatives aimed in the exchange of views in the context of the development of innovative solutions for agri-food supply chains.

NextFOOD's collaboration with [LOC-FOOD](#) includes a number of initiatives that commenced in May 2020 with the aim to promote regional foods and the sustainable economic and social development of rural areas through the synergy of the two projects. LOC-FOOD is an EU-funded project that endeavours to enable the promotion of traditional, local agri-food products by enhancing the portfolio of designated products of origin, establishing common marketing strategies and regional structures aiming at increasing visibility (at regional and international level), competitiveness, and trading opportunities.

Bilateral meetings between NextFOOD and [AG-CLUSTER](#), a cluster of agri-food professionals in the Region of Central Macedonia, Greece, have taken place with the aim to identify solutions for the promotion of innovation in local entrepreneurship (new and existing), to exchange knowledge and expertise, and to create networks to disseminate information between project members and third parties in the field of agriculture.

One-to-one dissemination workshops resulting in the exchange of banners have been held with the following projects: [AGRISAFE](#) (Horizon 2020), [aGROBOfood](#) (Horizon 2020), [Smart Farming](#) (Erasmus+ Adult). Moreover, NextFOOD outputs were presented in a networking [webinar](#) hosted by [INNOSETA](#).

2.2 Reporting of project synergies

Field	Input
Event title	NextFOOD - Innovative solutions in the field of agri-food supply chain
Type	Focus Group (3)
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	18-22 December 2020
Event aim & purpose	<p>Three virtual Focus Group meetings were organised in the spirit of co-creation and participation between Med Food TT Hubs, InoFA and NextFOOD. These events offered the opportunity for NextFOOD to join forces with two European projects as well as a pool of recognised experts engaged in the agri-food and traceability sectors.</p> <p>The Greek Focus Group was constituted by external stakeholders including farmers, agri-food producers (e.g., fruit, meat or fish producers), technology providers, local authorities and institutions.</p> <p>The first step was to inform the participants about the three programs, their scopes and objectives, as well as Focus Group's role throughout project's activities. Once the</p>

	<p>introductory part finished, it was time for interactive and fruitful discussions. The participants shared their experience on the challenges they currently face in the agri-food sector, as well as shed light on the needs and requirements for the implementation of traceability procedures.</p> <p>By the end of the day, both organisers and Focus Group members were extremely satisfied feeling that they all provided a valid contribution to our project.</p>
Type of audience	Farmers, agri-food producers (e.g., fruits, meat or fish producers), standard organisation, technology providers, local authorities and institutions
Estimated size of targeted audience	45
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	AFS

<p>Cluster "Internet of Food Alliance – InoFA"</p> <p><i>InoFA aims to the technological upgrade of the food retail supply chain through the development of digital solutions, which will incorporate cutting-edge technologies, such as Internet of Things, and will serve the needs of the whole value chain, from producer to consumer.</i></p>		
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Field	Input
Event title	ENOAT workshop online (European Network of Organic Agriculture Teachers)
Type	International conference
Place	<i>University of Maribor Faculty of Agriculture and Life Sciences</i>
Dates	August 27, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Knowledge exchange: Didactic activities in every University; presentations focused on co-learning
Relevance to the project	To disseminate the NF educational model to teaching practitioners in the field of food and agriculture.
Type of audience	Researchers and teachers in the agricultural/forestry/food sector

Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Geographical scope of event	European
Partner(s) involved	SLU, NMBU
Goal of presence	Dissemination, bring attention to the NF educational model and teaching material produced online by NextFOOD, to get feedback from experienced teachers in the field on the project outcomes.
Feedback from the audience	Interested and wanted to learn more
Stakeholders engaged	http://enoat.chil.me

Field	Input
Event title	Meeting in the Erasmus+ project 'Planet Friendly Schools'
Type	Meeting/Workshop
Place	Online
Dates	December 14, 2020
Event aim & purpose	To discuss and plan the project, including collecting relevant experiences from other ongoing projects in which partners are involved, including the NF project.
Relevance to the project	The event supported awareness of the NF project, dissemination of preliminary results, feedback from relevant researchers and new potential relations.
Type of audience	Researchers and practitioners within the fields of sustainable food systems, food and children, food and schools, environmental education.
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
Geographical scope of event	European
Partner(s) involved	Stine Rosenlund Hansen Niels Heine Kristensen - RUC
Goal of presence	To present the NF project, preliminary results and future plans focusing on WP1, receive feedback and establish new relevant networks.
Feedback from the audience	The participants expressed that the presented results, ideas and plans were highly interesting and relevant.

Stakeholders engaged	Researchers and practitioners within the fields of sustainable food systems, food and children, food and schools, environmental education
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Field	Input
Event title	NextFOOD / Newbie joint meeting
Type	Networking
Place	Online meeting
Dates	January 26, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of this event was to meet the NEWBIE team to share knowledge and discuss possible synergies.
Type of audience	This joint activity calls for further collaboration related to dissemination of results and integration of tools and models.
Estimated size of targeted audience	12 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	 SLU, NMBU, RUC, LU, USB, UNIBO, AFS
Feedback from the audience	Positive to further collaboration

Field	Input
Event Title	Synergy among RUBIZMO and NextFOOD
Place	Microsoft Teams, 15:00 CET
Dates	March 16, 2021
Stakeholder/Multiplier	Multiplayer meeting
Participants	 Martin Melin Justin Casimir (RISE Sweden Research Institutes of Sweden AB) Daphne Kapsala (ACRCM) Elena Kopanarova (ACRCM) Apostolina Tsaltampasi (ACRCM)
Position	The aim of the meeting was the explore the opportunities for cooperation among the two Horizon projects in terms of exchange of good practices, promotion of deliverables and

	<p>interaction in the scientific implementation of their work.</p> <p>RUBIZMO identify business models with high potential for empowering rural communities to take advantage of the opportunities arising from improved value chain optimization. RUBIZMO have created the following results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual Library of business cases and practices (Business Tool 1) • Guidelines for support the business environment (Business Tool 2) • Supply tool for improving collaboration (Business Tool 3) • Online transformation tool (Business Tool 4) • Online educational materials (Master class modules)
Expected outreach	<p>The synergy with RUBIZMO is expected to affect the business orientation and specifically the case studies and the work delivers by SEKEM Development Foundation (Case study 10), University of Oradea (Case study 2) and Welthungerhilfe (Case study 9).</p>
Results	<p>Next steps in our collaboration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RUBIZMO is planning on 23rd March - VIRTUAL STUDY VISIT in Pomacle-Bazancourt biorefinery: a major center of European bioeconomy. The interested partners can register here: https://rise.zoom.us/meeting/register/u5Eld-6pqj0sGtZPZM5kktWyIXMy7RJntJZE • RUBIZMO will invite NEXT FOOD experts to participate in the RUBIZMO Café Talks in April and May 2021. • RUBIZMO is interested to coach entrepreneurs from rural area and willing to promote this activity though NEXT FOOD project • RUBIZMO is going to invite our project manager at the final event of this project at October 2021.
	<p>Specifically, we have been invited to participate in the April Sessions of RUBIZMO Café talks & virtual visits (see more details attached) with topic “Carbon, issue or added value for agriculture and rural areas”. A series of quick and easy to access 30-minute “Café sessions” and virtual visits</p>

	<p>is taking place every Tuesday 11-11:30 CET as presented below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 13th April- VIRTUAL STUDY VISIT - Ecosystem Services (1h30 hours) by Dunhill Ekopark (Ireland) and Barycz Valley (Poland) • 20th April - Ola Petersson, RISE - Fossil free energy solutions of today and tomorrow • 27th April - Tora Råberg, RISE - What is biochar and how to use it?
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Field	Input
Event Title	RUBIZMO EU Projects Collaboration Meeting
Place	Microsoft Teams, 15:00 CET
Dates	May 17, 2021
Stakeholder/Multiplier	Multiplayer meeting by ACRCM and AFS
Name	Synergy among RUBIZMO, NextFOOD, PoliRURAL, Ruritage
Participants	Projects attended: NextFOOD, PoliRURAL, Ruritage, RUBIZMO
Position	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Following brief presentation (attached in email) on proposal for Summer School, a discussion took place. • It was reiterated that the topics for the Summer School presented are a starting point and can be changed or mixed up. • While some of the projects' tools are targeted at one particular set of stakeholders, they are all relevant for the Summer School as the focus will be on training and learning. • The Summer School is about making the various stakeholders; whether these are policy makers, farm advisors, business advisors, support agencies, educators, trainers, funding agencies etc., aware that these tools exist and equip them with the knowledge of how these tools can be used to support and enhance their work. • Need to think about who we want to target and who will use the tools.

- Suggested each project to target or headhunt 5-10 potential users of their tools and invite them to participate in the Summer School.
- As each session will last between 2 and 2.5 hours it is important that we use our time wisely.
- The sessions may be more productive by sending material – details of the tools, links to the tools, any demonstration videos, to participants in advance of each session so they can become familiar with the tools, test them and have questions or feedback prepared coming to the session.
- The session itself can then focus on why and how the tool will benefit them in their work and answer any questions they may have on using the tool.
- One way to approach the sessions could be to categorise the users of the tools into three categories and then match the tools that would best suit them into each category for e.g.
 - Policy makers and Business Environment user – what tools would these be most interested in?
 - Practical users such as Farm/Business advisors etc. and;
 - Educators, trainers and funders.
- The important thing to remember is who are the core user groups of your project and tools.

Next Steps:

- RUBIZMO will draft a template of how the sessions would work and welcome your input in this.

Since the meeting on Monday RUBIZMO had further ideas on what else could be included as part of the sessions

- Information with registration link to all three sessions/themes/topics – the participants can attend more than one session.
- With the registration confirmation send very brief material and link to websites of the consortiums/projects
- Hold introductory session
- Send information with login-details for trials
- Offer a café/support session (well-staffed!) to do hands-on trials or if they experience any difficulties accessing the material
- At beginning of the second session give brief summary of the first theme
- Repeat this process for each session.

Field	Input
Event title	<i>Synergies between RUBIZMO and NextFOOD projects</i>
Type	Online meeting
Place	Romania (Oradea-Bucharest)
Dates	May 26, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To identify synergies between the two projects in discussion; to exchange information and materials developed in the two projects (e.g. Canvas), to find new forms of cooperation between the participants.
Relevance to the project	Dissemination/Sharing of NextFOOD results with other European projects
Type of audience	Academic staff, researchers, farmers, representatives of farmer associations
Estimated size of targeted audience	16 persons
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	UNIOR, ACRCM ARAD association, partner within Rubizmo project University of Oradea, partner within NextFOOD Representatives of Crisana Association, Romanian Association for Sustainable Agriculture
Goal of presence	The goal was to disseminate relevant information on the NextFOOD project, to exchange materials developed within the two projects and to find new ways of cooperation even after the end of the two projects
Feedback from the audience	It was a successful meeting in which many initiatives have been taken into discussion.
Stakeholders engaged	The ACRCM promoted a fruitful collaboration between two key partners: 1. University of ORADEA, partner and leader of the Romanian Case of NextFOOD project: Students and farmers taking food innovations from idea to market: A practice-oriented course in food innovation including all the steps necessary to bring a new product to the market (Read more: https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-2-students-and-farmers-taking-food-innovations-from-idea-to-market/) and 2. ARAD Association partner of RUBIZMO project which developed "THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS "CAMELINA OMEGA 3 PLUS", "Agrarian Economy and Rural Development-Realities and

Perspectives for Romania", (Read more: <https://mpira.ub.uni-muenchen.de/106299/>)

Apart of the dissemination of relevant information and the exchange of materials developed between the two projects the goal was the exploration of new ways of cooperation even after the end of the two projects on topics such as: biodynamic agriculture, viticulture, organic wines, bio-pesticides, local seeds bank.

<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/synergy-of-the-university-of-oradea-and-arad-romanian-association-for-sustainable-agriculture-in-the-framework-of-horizon2020-projects-nextfood-and-rubizmo/>

Field	Input
Event title	Sustainability matters - novel tools to transform education and businesses
Type	Online event in collaboration with SDGs Labs
Place	Zoom (online)
Dates	December 13, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The objective of the peer learning meetings is to share experiences between cases and facilitate generation of new knowledge regarding action learning and action research. In this particular meeting, the case representatives discussed multi-actor involvement in the casework and how to implement action learning in an online setting.
Relevance to the project	Dissemination of the NextFOOD project and the Toolbox in particular
Type of audience	This event is aimed at educators and trainers of adults in all fields. It will introduce innovative methods used by European projects and

	universities to enhance sustainable practice and action
Estimated size of targeted audience	50-100
Geographical scope of event	Global
Partner(s) involved	NMBU and ISEKI
Goal of presence	Dissemination of the project (To encourage use of the <u>SDGs Labs</u> and NextFOOD online tools)

Field	Input
Place	Virtual meeting on Zoom
Dates	March 11, 2021
Stakeholder/Multiplier	Multiplayer meeting
Name	Synergy among LIAISON and NextFOOD
Participants	<p>Susanne von Münchhausen, Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development (Germany): Susanne.vonMuenchhausen@hnee.de</p> <p>Mark Redman, Highclere Consulting (Romania): mark@highclere-consulting.com</p> <p>Dona Pickard, INSTITUTE FOR THE STUDY OF SOCIETIES AND KNOWLEDGE (Bulgaria): dona.pickard@gmail.com</p> <p>Elena Kopanarova and Daphne Kapsala (ACRCM)</p>
Position	<p>The aim of the meeting was to explore the opportunities for cooperation among the two Horizon projects in terms of exchange of good practices, promotion of deliverables and interaction in the scientific implementation of their work. The LIAISON project aims to make contribution to optimizing interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of EU policies to seed up innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. They were very interested to cooperate with NEXT FOOD projects in different levels as discussed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation or dissemination of their focus groups planned for the next week. These will be promoted to the AFS and other local partners/universities. • Promotion of their event at social media • Structuring a meeting with the research team and project manager
Expected outreach	The LIAISON is aiming at interaction with education but is not going further in this point, which they expected to be covered by NEXT FOOD

Results	<p>project. They are very interested in sharing questionnaires with our focus groups.</p> <p>We consider that fruitful cooperation can be set with this project and specific activities can be presented. They have already involved the project in their website: Related Projects and Networks LIAISON2020 https://liaison2020.eu/our-network/related-projects/</p> <p>Steps in our cooperation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To share with them PPT of the project and the ACRCM • Sharing the details of the project (PPT about their current process) with all the partners. • Including more information about them at our next newsletter • Sperate introduction to NF Project Coordinator and arrangement of meeting with the participation of the project manager of NEXT food • Participation in roundtable for education in June 2021
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Field	Input
Event Title	Synergy among NEFERTITI and NextFOOD
Place	Microsoft Teams
Dates	April 1, 2021
Stakeholder/Multiplier	Multiplayer meeting
Participants 	Adrien GUICHAOUA, ACTA FR Martin Melin (SLU) Daphne Kapsala (ACRCM) Elena Kopanarova (ACRCM) Apostolina Tsaltampasi (ACRCM)
Position	The aim of the meeting was the explore the opportunities for cooperation among the two Horizon projects in terms of exchange of good practices, promotion of deliverables and interaction in the scientific implementation of their work.

	NEFERTITI is a unique project that establishes 10 interactive thematic networks and bring together 45 regional clusters (hubs) of demo-farmers and the involved actors (advisors, NGOs, industry, education, researchers and policy makers) in 17 countries. NEFERTITI focuses on creating added value from the exchange of knowledge, actors, farmers and technical content over the networks in order to boost innovation uptake, to improve peer to peer learning and network connectivity between farms actors across Europe, thus contributing to a more competitive, sustainable and climate-smart agriculture.
Expected outreach	The synergy with NEFERTITI is expected to affect networking possibilities among the members of both projects.
Results	<p>We consider that fruitful cooperation can be set with this project and specific activities can be presented. We have discussed the following possibilities for cooperation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To share with them PPT of the project • Sharing the details of the project (PPT about their current process) with all the partners. • Including more information about them at our next newsletter • To be involved in the steps of policy dialogue with EU Regions to match farmers and policy makers' interests in view of the networks sustainability.

Field	Input
Event title	Synergy of NextFOOD and LOC-FOOD
Type	Technical Meeting
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	May 21, 2021

Event aim & purpose	Memorandum of cooperation of the ACRCM with International Hellenic University (IHU) through their partnership in NextFOOD project.
Relevance to the project	LOC-FOOD and NEXT FOOD project explored ways in which the two projects can collaborate to promote regional foods and to help support the agri-food economy of the region and stressed the need for sustainable economic and social development in rural areas, with initiatives that include environmental, social and economic dimensions aimed at enhancing regional cooperation through the synergy of NextFOOD and LOC-FOOD projects.
Type of audience	Academics, Regional Consultants, Executive Staff
Estimated size of targeted audience	6
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM, IHU
Goal of presence	The aim of this collaboration is to identify agri-food products whose quality and interesting characteristics make them suitable candidates for certification under the European Union's quality scheme as PDO, PGI, or TSG. This action forms part of the international project 'Local Development and Cross Border Cooperation in the area of Agricultural Products and Traditional Food' funded by the Joint Operational Programme Black Sea Basin 2014-2020, part of the EU's Black Sea Cross Border Cooperation Programme.
Feedback from the audience	The overall coordinator of the project is the Department of Co-funded Regional Development Programmes of the Ministry of the Interior (Sector Macedonia and Thrace). The coordinator at IHU is Professor Maria Papageorgiou of the Department of Food Science and Technology. ACRCM is contributing to the LOC-FOOD project through its role as informal partner to IHU
Stakeholders engaged	Useful links: LOC FOOD project Food Science and Technology Department of the International Hellenic University of Thessaloniki, Greece Agronutritional Cooperation Region Central Macedonia

3 Dissemination and training activities

3.1 Event reporting by date (May 2020 – April 2022)

3.1.1 May 2020

Type and Number of Events:

- Online Workshop (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Skogforsk case - meeting
Type	Educational meeting/ Workshop
	Because of the Covid-10 situation the case-meeting was organised as a digital meeting on mobile phones and computers. Participants from different places: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The machine operators and the project leader from forest sites in northern Sweden. • The expert from a harvesting site in the middle of Sweden. • The researcher from home in the middle of Sweden.
Dates	May 26, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Educational meeting and workshop - <i>Increased quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity (Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain)</i>
Relevance to the project	WP 2 Case study – forestry professionals. We will adapt the model to fit our learners and the environment in which they work. The meetings take place at logging sites where we together look at the site – before, during and after harvesting activities and have reflective dialogues on methods and results in relation to the goal to create high value micro habitats in the forest.
Type of audience	Forest machine operators
Geographical scope of event	Local/ National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	Education and action research
Stakeholders engaged	Forest company

3.1.2 June 2020

Type and Number of Events:

- WP/Partners Meeting/digital (1)
- Partners Conference/digital (1)

Field	Input
Event title	WP1 Meeting
Type	Meeting between WP1 partners
Place	Online
Dates	June 4, 202
Event aim & purpose	To present and discuss preliminary results of the previous work in Wp1 and create a roadmap for the upcoming year.
Relevance to the project	Ensure collaboration between partners and progress in WP1.
Type of audience	Wp1 partners
Estimated size of targeted audience	16
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	RUC, LU, SLU, ISEKI, University of Calcutta, Universidad De Chile, CIHEAM
Goal of presence	Ensure collaboration between partners and progress in WP1

The banner features a green background with wheat stalks. Text includes 'NEXT FOOD'S' at the top, 'Partners meeting' in a yellow script font on a black brushstroke, 'ONLINE CONFERENCE' in white, and the 'Next FOOD' logo on the right. Below the logo, it says 'GO DIGITAL' and '3-5 JUNE 2020'.

<p>Partners' Conference 03 - 05 June 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Wednesday 03.06.2020 14.00 -16.00</p> <p>Catch-up session to get a shared understanding of the whole project. Moderator: SLU</p> <p>16.00-16.30 Coffee and small-talk "together" in small groups</p>

16.30 -17.30

Follow-up on the financial situation in the project. Moderator: SLU

Thursday 04.06.2020

11.00- 14:00

Demonstration of preliminary results and feedback from the consortium, part I

- Introduction, 11.00-11.15, moderator AFS
- WP1 audit tool, 11.15-12.15, moderator RUC
- WP2 and WP3 toolbox, 12.30-14.00, moderator NMBU

Afternoon: Individual WP-meetings, if desired.

Friday 05.06.2020

11.00- 14.30

Demonstration of preliminary results and feedback from the consortium, Part II

- WP4 gender and forthcoming activities, 11.00-12.00, moderator WHH and UNIBO
- WP5 assessment framework, 12.15-13.15, moderator LU
- WP6 data management and stakeholder plan, 13.30-14.30, moderator AFS

14.45-15.45

Wrap-up session. Moderator: SLU

- Implications for what we should be doing during the next 6 months
- Evaluation of meeting. What have we learned about Zoom-meetings?

All presentation are available here:

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-M8VJ-nLFnRzjol3ou6g

3.1.3 July 2020

Type and Number of Events:

- Focus Group (1)
- Workshops (8) on task 4.2 (July - December 2020)

Field	Input
Event title	Workshops on task 4.2
Type	Online/ in person workshops
Place	Online/ In person; 7 workshops are in Europe, 2 workshops are in other continents (1 in Chile, 1 in India).
Dates	From July 2020 to December 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event was held to identify strategies for policy improvement in agri-food and forestry education and training systems.
Relevance to the project	Identifying options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios helps directly Task 4.2 partners in their research activity.
Type of audience	A large number of professionals involved in AFF education, training, and policy.
Number of workshops	9
Geographical scope of the events	8 workshops are with a national scope, 1 workshop is with an international scope.
Estimated size of targeted audience	60
Estimated average duration	2 hours
Partner(s) involved	LU, UNIOR, AFS, ACRCM, SKOGFORSK, CIHEAM, WHH, IFA, RUC, UCH
Feedback from the partners	The workshops were positively received by the partners both in the organization and in the discussion arose in the meetings. Indeed, the unusual roundtable with different AKIS actors allowed us to examine relationships, gaps, ideas, and proposals in the AFF sectors.

Results

The quantity of information and suggestions is very wide. However, some themes were mentioned more and more in-depth were discussed. Particularly:

- Skills and competencies needed in the sector (mainly confirmed WP1 skill list);
- The need to update curriculums, and complement formal education with extracurricular activities. Three words to describe the curriculums of the future: short, flexible, digital;
- The necessity of increasing the attractiveness of all the AFF sectors to new target groups (e.g., youth in urban areas);
- The importance of life-long learning was also underlined and reported as fundamental for future challenges;
- Enhance collaboration, dialogue and coordination among the main stakeholders of the sector (i.e. farmers, industry, policymakers, local society, universities/research institutes);
- The need to integrate the topic of sustainability in education, starting from early ages (collaboration with schools);
- There is a need to empower consumers regarding the importance of healthy and sustainable diets (*responsible consumption*);
- The topic of gender: to make the sector gender-neutral by providing equal rights to women in the whole sector, in addition to policy-making and decision-making about the education and training policies.

Field	Input
Event title	Testing the NextFOOD Impact Framework – The Swedish Pilot
Type	Focus group 1, Potatoes
Place	Borgeby, Sweden
Dates	July 22, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The aim is to test the NextFOOD Impact Framework, disclose its strengths and weaknesses, and make suggestions for further refinement.
Relevance to the project	This contributes to the aim of developing an assessment framework for defining and

	evaluating the quality of interactive innovation and practice-oriented research in the agri-food and forestry sector.
Type of audience	Farmers, producer organisations, university researchers
Estimated size of targeted audience	5
Geographical scope of event	The focus group takes place on a national level
Partner(s) involved	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	To create an action plan for the evaluation by assembling a group and involving them in the planning
Feedback from the audience	The focus group discussions were very interesting.
Stakeholders engaged	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences; Potatisodlarna (Producer organisation); Svensk Potatis (certifying organisation)

3.1.4 August 2020

Type and Number of Events:

- Digital Workshop (2)

Field	Input
Event title	Workshop on task 4.2
Type	Online workshop
Place	Online (due to Covid restrictions)
Dates	August 26, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event was held to identify strategies for policy improvement in agri-food and forestry education and training systems.
Relevance to the project	To identify options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios helps directly Task 4.2 partners in their research activity.
Type of audience	Researchers, HR manager, professors, labour market expert
Estimated size of targeted audience	10
Geographical scope of event	Sweden/ National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk, Lund University

Field	Input
Event title	ENOAT workshop online (European Network of Organic Agriculture Teachers)
Type	International conference

Place	<i>University of Maribor Faculty of Agriculture and Life Sciences</i>
Dates	August 27, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Knowledge exchange: Didactic activities in every University; presentations focused on co-learning
Relevance to the project	To disseminate the NF educational model to teaching practitioners in the field of food and agriculture.
Type of audience	Researchers and teachers in the agricultural/forestry/food sector
Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Geographical scope of event	European
Partner(s) involved	SLU, NMBU
Goal of presence	Dissemination, bring attention to the NF educational model and teaching material produced online by NextFOOD, to get feedback from experienced teachers in the field on the project outcomes.
Feedback from the audience	Interested and wanted to learn more
Stakeholders engaged	http://enoat.chil.me

3.1.5 September 2020

Type and Number of Events:

- WP/Partners Meeting/Digital (2)
- Workshop/Digital (5)
- Focus Group/Digital (2)

Field	Input
Event title	NF Coordination workshop
Type	Project workshop
Place	SLU (Online)
Dates	1-3 September 2020
Event aim & purpose	Promote the coordination of activities in the NextFOOD project; identify synergies and possible overlaps; set an action plan for the way forward;
Relevance to the project	The need for coordination and an improved overview of the whole project has been raised by NF partners.
Type of audience	NF work package and task leaders
Estimated size of targeted audience	15
Geographical scope of event	European
Partner(s) involved	The NF Consortium

Goal of presence	To come up with an action plan for increased coordination among different activities of the NF project.
Feedback from the audience	Positive, this kind of activities are needed

Field	Input
Event title	Skogforsk case - meeting
Type	Educational meeting/ Workshop
Place	Because of the Covid-10 situation the case-meeting was organised as a digital meeting on mobile phones and computers. Participants from different places: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The machine operators and the project leader from a forest sites in northern Sweden. • The expert from a harvesting site in the middle of Sweden. • The researcher from home in the middle of Sweden.
Dates	September 8, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Educational meeting and workshop - <i>Increased quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity (Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain)</i>
Relevance to the project	WP 2 Case study – forestry professionals. We will adapt the model to fit our learners and the environment in which they work. The meetings take place at logging sites where we together look at the site – before, during and after harvesting activities and have reflective dialogues on methods and results in relation to the goal to create high value micro habitats in the forest.
Type of audience	Forest machine operators
Geographical scope of event	Local/ National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	Education and action research
Stakeholders engaged	Forest company

Field	Input
Event title	Policy Workshop

Type	Workshop
Place	Kolkata, India (Online)
Dates	September 8, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event was held to identify strategies for policy improvement in agri-food and forestry education and training systems.
Relevance to the project	To identify options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios helps directly Task 4.2 partners in their research activity.
Type of audience	Administrator, policy makers, professors from various universities and education institutes
Estimated size of targeted audience	8
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Welthungerhilfe and University of Calcutta
Goal of presence	The workshop helped us in gathering input from policy makers/influencers on identifying options and strategies for improving the educational policy framework, with specific reference to Farm to Form strategies. Which will eventually help to propose new policy instruments for policy reform in education and training to achieve a sustainable agri-food systems.
Feedback from the audience	The group, through discussion came out with specific inputs on farm to food strategies.

Field	Input
Event title	Workshop on task 4.2
Type	Online workshop
Place	Online (due to Covid restrictions)
Dates	September 21, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event was held to identify strategies for policy improvement in agri-food and forestry education and training systems.
Relevance to the project	To identify options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios helps directly Task 4.2 partners in their research activity.
Type of audience	Vocational education experts, a university professor, one industry officer, one food policy officer.

Partner(s) involved	 LUND UNIVERSITY	LUND
Estimated size of targeted audience	5	
Geographical scope of event	Denmark/ National	

Field	Input
Event title	WP6 PROGRESS ONLINE MEETING
Type	WP6 Partners meeting
Dates	22 & 23 September, 2020
Event aim & purpose	<p>Tuesday, Sep 22, 2020 14:00 - 16:45 (CEST)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome & Introduction: Catch-up session & feedback from the NF Workshop held 3rd of September at (WP6 + WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5) • Follow up on the progress of DEO update - Discussion • EIP – Abstracts: Follow up – Discussion • Follow up on Social Media • Follow up on Animation Clip – Discussion <p>Wednesday, Sep 23, 2020 14:00 - 17:00 (CEST)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Platform: progress, changes, defects – Discussion • Progress on Events and their documentation – Discussion • Newsletters: progress and required changes – Discussion • Gender – sensitive communication • Follow-up on the DMP update – Discussion
Relevance to the project	Follow up on the progress of WP6
Type of audience	Researchers, Project Managers
Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM, ISEKI, BIOINSTITUT, SLU, AFS, MEKELE, UCHILE
Goal of presence	Project dissemination and feedback

Field	Input
Event title	Testing the NextFOOD Impact Framework – The Swedish Pilot
Type	Focus group 2, Dairy cows
Place	Digital meeting, Sweden

Dates	September 24, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The aim is to test the NextFOOD Impact Framework, disclose its strengths and weaknesses, and make suggestions for further refinement of the framework.
Relevance to the project	This contributes to the aim of developing an assessment framework for defining and evaluating the quality of interactive innovation and practice-oriented research in the agri-food and forestry sector.
Type of audience	Service technicians to farmers, advisory service organisations, university researchers
Estimated size of targeted audience	8
Geographical scope of event	The focus group takes place on a national level.
Partner(s) involved	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	To create an action plan for the evaluation by assembling a group and involving them in the planning
Feedback from the audience	The focus group discussions were very interesting.
Stakeholders engaged	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences; Växa Sverige (advisory service organisation); Service technicians to farmers.

Field	Input
Event title	Workshop on task 4.2
Type	Workshop (online)
Place	Santiago, Chile
Dates	September 24, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event was held to identify strategies for policy improvement in agri-food and forestry education and training systems in Chile and Latin America.
Relevance to the project	To identify options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios helps directly Task 4.2 partners in their research activity.
Type of audience	Experts in the field of agri-food policies and education.
Estimated size of targeted audience	5 (3 female and 2 male)

Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Chile
Goal of presence	Role as moderator
Feedback from the audience	Input on agri-food public policies in Chile and Latin America.

Field	Input
Event title	Teacher's Workshop
Type	Brainstorming session
Place	Kolkata, India (Online)
Dates	September 25, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Brainstorming session with the course teachers to get feedforward on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall structure of the course - How to conduct the course online, interestingly? - What kind of support do you need to conduct online classes?
Relevance to the project	Part of WP2 – teacher's workshop before the case course
Type of audience	Teachers and facilitators of the course
Estimated size of targeted audience	9
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Welthungerhilfe and University of Calcutta
Goal of presence	This workshop was important to get input from the course facilitators on the course structure, content and methodologies.
Feedback from the audience	The following things were concluded <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The course administrator will attend all the sessions and inform others about the previous classes, so that a continuity is maintained - The teachers/facilitators can attend other's session

- Online interactive tools need to be shared with everyone, so that facilitators can use them and make the sessions as interesting as possible.

Field	Input
Event title	Testing the NextFOOD Impact Framework – The Swedish Pilot
Type	Focus group 3 , Bureaucracy
Place	Digital meeting, Sweden
Dates	September 28, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The aim is to test the NextFOOD Impact Framework, disclose its strengths and weaknesses, and make suggestions for further refinement of the framework.
Relevance to the project	This contributes to the aim of developing an assessment framework for defining and evaluating the quality of interactive innovation and practice-oriented research in the agri-food and forestry sector.
Type of audience	Farmers' organisation, advisory service organisations, university researchers
Estimated size of targeted audience	4
Geographical scope of event	The focus group takes place on a national level
Partner(s) involved	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	To create an action plan for the evaluation by assembling a group and involving them in the planning
Feedback from the audience	The focus group discussions were very interesting.
Stakeholders engaged	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences; Växa Sverige (advisory service organisation); Hushållningssällskapet Halland (advisory service organisation); The Federation of Swedish Farmers (Farmers' organisation)

3.1.6 October 2020

Type and Number of Events:

- Seminar (1)
- Online Focus Group (3)
- Online Workshop (2)
- Workshop (1)
- Networking (1)
- Book Release (1)
- Online session (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Workshop on task 4.2
Type	Online workshop
Place	Online (due to Covid restrictions)
Dates	October 8, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event was held to identify strategies for policy improvement in agri-food and forestry education and training systems.
Relevance to the project	To identify options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios helps directly Task 4.2 partners in their research activity.
Type of audience	Farmer's union employee, Norwegian Agricultural Cooperative employee, Norwegian Agency for Quality Enhancement in Higher Education officer, a researcher
Estimated size of targeted audience	4 (2 male and 2 female)
Geographical scope of event	Norway
Partner(s) involved	NMBU
	<p>Norwegian University of Life Sciences</p>
Goal of presence	Assisting WP4 in their work
Feedback from the audience	The audience were happy to share their opinions, said the conversation was very inspiring and two of them said to contact them later if we needed more participants in future events.

Field	Input
Event title	Workshop on task 4.2
Type	Online workshop
Place	Online (due to Covid restrictions)
Dates	October 8, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event was held to identify strategies for policy improvement in agri-food and forestry education and training systems.
Relevance to the project	To identify options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios helps directly Task 4.2 partners in their research activity.
Type of audience	Advisers, representatives of accreditation bodies, training associations in the food sector, representatives of farmers' confederation.
Estimated size of targeted audience	7 (5 male and 2 female)
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association
Goal of presence	As part of WP4, task 4.2, ISEKI-Food Association was asked to organise and hold a focus group discussion with the aim to identify strategies for policy improvement of research and education in the field of agri-food and forestry, by identifying options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios. To further that objective, the focus group discussion concentrated on the ISEKI case in the NextFOOD project, the International Student Competition; and to the ISEKI problem related to policy: no recognition of non-university activities for university credit, (in the broader picture, particularly a problem for skills training as applied to sustainable food systems). A report written by ISEKI-Food Association was sent to the WP4-leader after the focus group conduction.
Stakeholders engaged	Participants of the focus group represented accreditation bodies, training associations in the food sector and representatives of farmers' confederation.

Field	Input
Event title	NextFOOD - Innovative solutions in the field of agri-food supply chain
Type	Focus Group (3)
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	October 18-22, 2020

Event aim & purpose

As the last days of 2020 rolled around, our Greek partners had a mission: having the Quadruple Helix Stakeholders shed light on the challenges facing the local agri-food supply chain.

Between 18 and 22 December, three virtual Focus Group meetings were organised in the spirit of co-creation and participation. These events were also the occasion of NextFOOD to join effort with two European projects as well as a pool of recognised experts engaged in the agri-food and traceability sectors.

The Greek Focus Group reflected a balanced blend of different organisation types, stakeholders and expertise, providing a good representativeness of Greek food supply-chain. More specifically, it has been constituted by external stakeholders and auditors in representation of farmers, agri-food producers (e.g. fruits, meat or fish producers), standard organisation, technology providers, local authorities and institutions.

The events have been co-organised and co-lead by the AFS, *Green Projects* and *CERTH*. The first step was to inform the participants about the tree programs, their scopes and objectives, as well as Focus Group’s role throughout project’s activities. Once the introductory part finished, it was time for interactive and fruitful discussions! The participants shared their experience on the challenges they currently face in the agri-food sector, as well as shed light on the needs and requirements for the implementation of traceability procedures.

By the end of the day, both organisers and Focus Group members were extremely satisfied feeling

	that they all provided a valid contribution to our project.
Type of audience	Farmers, agri-food producers (e.g. fruits, meat or fish producers), standard organisation, technology providers, local authorities and institutions
Estimated size of targeted audience	45
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	AFA

Field	Input
Event title	NextFOOD Audit Tool Test
Type	Workshop
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	October 21, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The aim of the workshop was to gain in-depth insight into the content and structure of the NextFOOD Audit tool, for self-assessing skilling in agri-food and forestry education.
Relevance to the project	Through using the NextFOOD Audit Tool, students and teachers will discover how their education performs in relation to each skilling pathway. They will also be encouraged to reflect on ways to develop their educational activities further, along these pathways. This will provide them with insight concerning the capacities their organisation has for producing a next generation agri-food and forestry professionals.
Type of audience	Students of Perottis College
Estimated size of targeted audience	15
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	AFS Roskilde University Lund University

Field	Input
Event title	Subject group meeting for Business Management at SLU
Type	Seminar
Place	SLU (Online)
Dates	October 21, 2020
Event aim & purpose	Discussion on interesting research projects relevant to the field and dissemination of the education model in NF.

Relevance to the project	To shortly introduce the NF project to researchers and bring attention to the toolbox for teachers.
Type of audience	Researchers and teachers in the agricultural/forestry/food sector
Estimated size of targeted audience	10
Geographical scope of event	Swedish / National
Partner(s) involved	SLU
Goal of presence	Bring attention to the teaching material produced online by NextFOOD

Field	Input
Event title	Progress of the Master in Agroecology and Food Sovereignty
Type	Dissemination in Social Network about the new Master in Agroecology and Food Sovereignty
Place	Pollenzo (Bra), Italy
Dates	October 2020
Event aim & purpose	During the first month of the Master the students experienced different activities of action learning: interactive frontal lectures, garden activities, farm visits and dialogue with SlowFood communities
Relevance to the project	The new Master was developed within the project (WP3), it is an example of the new education program totally based on action learning approach
Type of audience	Formal and relevant students, young agricultural activists and stakeholders are audience of these posts
Estimated size of targeted audience	1000 readers
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	SlowFood, NMBU (Prof. Geir Lieblein), UNISG (Paola Migliorini, Natalia Rastrogueva, Charlotte Prelorentzos)
Goal of presence	the posts are targeted to inform about progress of the Master under COVID restrictions
Feedback from the audience	we had positive feedback

Event title:	Online Interaction Session on ‘How to Develop a model farm’
Type	Online session
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	
Event aim & purpose	The session was planned in order to provide students expert opinion on concepts related to sustainable farming. Students attending the short course on Agroecology and Action Learning can benefit from the session.
Relevance to the project	It provided an opportunity in improving inter-case collaborations and there by improves co-creation and dissemination of knowledge
Type of audience	Students and Farmers
Estimated size of targeted audience	12
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	University of Kerala WHH
Goal of presence	Centre for Agroecology and Public Health, by hosting the session used the opportunity for cross case collaborations and to learn from other cases.
Feedback from the audience	Students used the opportunity to clarify their apprehensions relating to agroecology and sustainable farming. In addition, it provided them with a new learning arena to familiarise with farming systems in another region
Stakeholders engaged	Students, Facilitators, Mentors

Event title	Release function of book titled ‘Block Panchayat as Change Agents in India’s Decentralization: The Kerala Experience’
Type	Book Release function / Networking
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	October 29, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The function was planned to release the book titled ‘Block Panchayat as Change Agents in India’s Decentralization’ co-authored by Dr.Manju S. Nair, Dr. Saisree K.G and Vijayasree.
Relevance to the project	The book documents agroecological interventions of Local Self Government, the stakeholder with which University of Kerala is joining hands to popularize agroecology.
Type of audience	Politicians, Bureaucrats, Academicians, Students
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Kerala State Resource Centre, Government of Kerala
Goal of presence	Centre for Agroecology and Public Health, by hosting the release function, facilitated the dialogue between administrators and academicians in matters relating to sustainable development and agroecological transition.
Feedback from the audience	The book was well received and it is an addition to the existing knowledge relating to decentralized administration and agroecological transition.
Stakeholders engaged	Hon. Minister (Finance, Govt. of Kerala), Academics

3.1.7 November 2020

Type and number of events:

- Workshop (2)
- Online workshop (1)
- Online seminar (1)
- PhD course (1)
- Certificate Course (1)

Field	Input
Event title	“Identification of strategies for improving the educational policy network”
Type	Workshop – WP4.2
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	November 12, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The ACRCM organised an online workshop with policy makers on the 12nd of November 2020. Final aim the identification of new policy instruments that will improve the education and training methods for the professionals in the agri-food and forestry system, in the framework of WP4.
Relevance to the project	In the context of the wider Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) the focus was on the identification of gaps in the current policies and the creation of desired policy outcomes that will support the transition towards action-oriented learning methods.
Type of audience	Policy makers, Presidents of chamber of commerce’s, Vice-governor of Agriculture Economy of RCM, Academics, Mayors of Municipalities of RCM, representatives of the Ministry of Agriculture of Greece
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM

Field	Input
Event title	Potential policy strategies for improvements in sustainable agriculture and forestry education
Type	Workshop

Place	Bari, Italy
Dates	November 18, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The event was held to identify strategies for policy improvement in agri-food and forestry education and training systems.
Relevance to the project	To identify options for improved policy instruments in different context scenarios helps directly Task 4.2 partners in their research activity.
Type of audience	Local stakeholders involved in educational policies at different levels: research institution, local authority, higher education/vocational, academia, farmers representative
Estimated size of targeted audience	7 participants (3 females, 4 males)
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	CIHEAM , Virginia Belsanti, Patrizia Pugliese, Suzana Madzaric
Goal of presence	Organiser/facilitator
Feedback from the audience	Very satisfied and happy for the fruitful exchange of views

Event title	Short Course on Agroecology: Action Research and Education
Type	One Month Certificate Course
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	18-11-2020 to 14-12-2020
Event aim & purpose	Providing post graduate students an opportunity to practice 'Next food' model of action learning and there by enhance competences like observation, reflection, dialoguing, participation and visioning so as to improve knowledge of agroecology.
Relevance to the project	Data generated from the course, including learner and client document, competence assessments will be used for research in the project and thus, the course forms the base of the project.
Type of audience	Students and Farmers
Estimated size of targeted audience	20 (including students, farmers and mentors)
Geographical scope of event	International

Partner(s) involved	University of Kerala WHH
Goal of presence	Centre for Agroecology hosts the course with an aim to popularize action research and education.
Feedback from the audience	The course acted as a platform for students from multi-disciplinary background to indulge in peer learning and, unlike the conventional learning systems provided students an opportunity for action learning
Stakeholders engaged	Students, Facilitators, Mentors, Farmers

Field	Input
Event title	PhD course: 'IMT-PhD: Food Studies and Agro-Ecology – methods, principles and values'
Type	PhD course organised by the NF team at Roskilde University in collaboration with Martin Melin
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	November 18- 20, 2020
Event aim & purpose	To introduce, discuss and explore problems, issues and potential solutions related to sustainable food systems, and the theories and methodologies used to study those.
Relevance to the project	The course introduced, discussed and explored some of the problems, issues and potential solutions dealt with in the NextFOOD project, as well as supported relations between the PhD students involved with the NF project, and with PhD students working with similar issues, but not involved with the project.

	To educate future researchers in co-learning education principles
Type of audience	PhD students inside and outside NF. The course had lectures by researchers not involved with NF and thereby spread knowledge of the project to these researchers, and established contacts that can be useful for future knowledge-sharing.
Estimated size of targeted audience	10
Geographical scope of event	Participants from DK, Sweden and Norway.
Partner(s) involved	Niels Heine Kristensen - NMBU Stine Rosenlund Hansen - RUC Martin Melin - SLU
Goal of presence	To organize the course, make presentations and provide feedback and input to students' work.
Feedback from the audience	The students expressed that the course had provided new insights into the field, especially the interdisciplinary perspective were useful. The strengthened relations with other PhD students were also highlighted. Students were very pleased with the course.
Stakeholders engaged	https://study.ruc.dk/class/view/23603

Event title:	NextFOOD (WP2) -Reflecting and planning the Agroecology Course in Kerala
Type	Workshop
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	November 16, 2020
Event aim & purpose	The objective of the Workshop was to do a reflection of the previous course in terms of the intended shifts that NextFOOD envisions and to plan for the upcoming course.
Relevance to the project	The workshop succeeded in refining the curriculum in order to conduct the course as a regular course to materialise the intended shifts envisioned in learning and research, abiding to the Covid 19 pandemic regulations in the state.
Type of audience	Audience (Participants) included students, mentors, researchers, teachers, policy makers
Estimated size of targeted audience	8

Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Kerala
Goal of presence	To participate in curriculum development of Short Course on Agroecology: Action Learning and Research and make suggestions for new curriculum development.
Feedback from the audience	The stakeholders contributed towards discussion with relevant points to refine the course such as conducting the interactive sessions with experts as online session, providing assignments to report environmental issues from locality etc.
Stakeholders engaged	Students from the previous course, facilitators

Field	Input
Event title	Learn more about collaborative projects in the EU research and innovation framework programme – Horizon Europe
Type	Seminar
Place	LU (Online)
Dates	November 20, 2020
Event aim & purpose	What are the benefits from participating in collaborative EU projects? Examples of experience from Lärosäten Syd
Relevance to the project	To shortly introduce the NF project to a wider audience and bring attention to dissemination material for those who are interested.
Type of audience	Researchers in the agricultural/forestry/food sector
Estimated size of targeted audience	60
Geographical scope of event	Swedish
Partner(s) involved	SLU, LU
Goal of presence	Bring attention to the NF project as a good example on collaborative EU research projects

3.1.8 December 2020

Type and number of events:

- Online WP/Partners Meeting (2)
- Workshop (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Meeting in the Erasmus+ project 'Planet Friendly Schools'
Type	Meeting/Workshop
Place	Online
Dates	December 14, 2020
Event aim & purpose	To discuss and plan the project, including collecting relevant experiences from other ongoing projects in which partners are involved, including the NF project.
Relevance to the project	The event supported awareness of the NF project, dissemination of preliminary results, feedback from relevant researchers and new potential relations.
Type of audience	Researchers and practitioners within the fields of sustainable food systems, food and children, food and schools, environmental education.
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
Geographical scope of event	European
Partner(s) involved	Stine Rosenlund Hansen Niels Heine Kristensen - RUC
Goal of presence	To present the NF project, preliminary results and future plans focusing on WP1, receive feedback and establish new relevant networks.
Feedback from the audience	The participants expressed that the presented results, ideas and plans were highly interesting and relevant.
Stakeholders engaged	Researchers and practitioners within the fields of sustainable food systems, food and children, food and schools, environmental education

Field	Input
Event title	1st Newsletter editorial board meeting
Type	Wp6 meeting
Place	Online meeting
Dates	December 17, 2020

Event aim & purpose	Creation of the final version of the internal NextFOOD newsletter Issue 6/2020
Type of audience	Newsletter working group, internal researchers of the project (WP6)
Estimated size of targeted audience	3 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	BIOINSTITUT, SLU, UCH

Field	Input
Event title	WP6 FINAL COMMUNICATION PLAN
Type	WP6 Partners meeting
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	December 10, 2020
Event aim & purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Catch-up session & feedback • Follow up on the progress of DEO update - Discussion • EIP – Abstracts: Follow up – Discussion • Follow up on Social Media • Platform: progress, changes, defects – Discussion • Progress on Events and their documentation – Discussion • Newsletters: progress and required changes – Discussion • Follow-up on the DMP update – Discussion
Relevance to the project	Follow up on the progress of WP6 and the FINAL COMMUNICATION PLAN
Type of audience	Researchers, Project Managers
Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM, ISEKI, BIOINSTITUT, SLU, AFS, MEKELE, UCHILE
Goal of presence	Project dissemination and feedback

3.1.9 January 2021

Type and number of events:

- Digital Workshop/Synergy (1)
- WP Partners meeting/digital (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Gender Mainstreaming in Research and Education
Type	Workshop
Place	Online partners meeting
Dates	January 18, 2021
Event aim & purpose	How to integrate gender-sensitive approach into research and teaching systems. Resources for gender training. Recruitment, selection and career development (unconscious bias; leadership development in academia; mentoring programs to support women's career development. Gender-sensitive communication 6.5 How to integrate gender in research and education contents/ curricula (GENDER-NET, IGAR etc.). Reporting tools for gender
Type of audience	NextFOOD partners
Estimated size of targeted audience	20 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	WHH, LU, Mekele, UNIBO, SLU
Feedback from the audience	Positive to further collaboration

Field	Input
Event title	NextFOOD / Newbie joint meeting
Type	Networking
Place	Online meeting
Dates	January 26, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of this event was to meet the NEWBIE team to share knowledge and discuss possible synergies.
Type of audience	This joint activity calls for further collaboration related to dissemination of results and integration of tools and models.
Estimated size of targeted audience	12 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	SLU, NMBU, RUC, LU, USB,

UNIBO,
AFS

Feedback from the audience

Positive to further collaboration

3.1.10 February 2021

Type and number of events:

- Digital Workshops (1)
- Conference (1)

Field	Input
Event title	FoodFactory-4-Us 2020-2021: Valorizing Food Biodiversity
Type	Conference
Place	Online
Dates	February 18, 2021
Event aim & purpose	In the FoodFactory-4-Us Sustainable Supply Chain International Student Competition student teams from universities worldwide competed in a game, based on participatory education and action learning to find the best solutions to how food biodiversity can be valorized. At the Final Virtual Conference student teams present their projects in front of a worldwide audience.
Relevance to the project	Case #4 is the FoodFactory-4-Us international student competition based on participatory education and action-learning.
Type of audience	
Estimated size of targeted audience	>110 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association
Goal of presence	To see and hear about interesting projects in the field of food biodiversity.

Feedback from the audience	We received very positive feedback from the audience. We had set up a google form and received more than 60 replies.
Stakeholders engaged	FoodFactory-4-Us: Valorizing Biodiversity ISEKI-Food Association (iseki-food.net)

Event title	Two Digital Meetings – Dissemination Activity
Type	Two digital meetings with local stakeholders and agricultural producers presenting the current stage of development of the NextFOOD project
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	February 23, 2021 – March 04 2021
Event aim & purpose	The ACRCM organised two digital meetings with local stakeholders and agricultural producers in order to promote and present the current stage of development of the NextFOOD project.
Type of audience	1st Meeting: 15 local producers and agricultural cooperatives 2nd Meeting: 22 experts of the AC RCM members
Estimated size of audience	50
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM
Goal of presence	The participants discussed the current situation of the agricultural sector and the problem they

are facing due the COVID -19 situation. Their indirect involvement in the NextFOOD project activities was debated together with the president of AC RCM, Mr. Konstantinos Kilitidis.

During the meeting were discussed the direct involvement of these organizations in the promotion of NEXT food results and how to enhance the impact of the project activities at regional level.

<http://agromacedonia.gr/news/enimerotiki-ekdilosi-nextfood-parousiasi-drason-acrcm-2021/>

NextFOOD's was presented to the participants in GREEK and is available in the following link: <https://youtu.be/RA7oAR4Nuug>

3.1.11 March 2021

Type and number of events:

- Online WP/Partners Meeting (2)
- Digital Workshops (3)
- Digital workshop/Synergy (2)
- Seminar (2)

Field	Input
Event title	Workshop on task 4.2
Type	Online workshop
Place	Online (due to Covid restrictions)
Dates	March 4, 2021

Event aim & purpose	The stakeholders selected to participate were experts of European education and training in AFF. Thus, the aim was to identify key points where policies can contribute to educating the next generation of professionals in the AFF system, coherently with the EU New Green Deal, Farm to Fork, and CAP reform.
Relevance to the project	The event was held to present the outcome of the local workshops and to collect feed-backs to develop an EU-level perspective on the education and training in AFF topic. In this sense, the workshop played a pivotal role in the project and the development of relevant final proposals.
Type of audience	Research and academia, international farmers organizations, and the European Commission.
Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Geographical scope of the event	EU
Partner(s) involved	All the WP leaders were involved
Feedback from the audience	The participants were struck both by the themes faced by the NextFOOD project and the results developed in the local workshop. The use of the AKIS framework and the will to spread action learning particularly impressed them. The partners who had already organised the local workshop in their context were positively surprised by the common dynamics that evolved in the other workshops. In particular, if on one hand all across Europe it is difficult to bring together the different AKIS actors, on the other hand, it is surprising how putting them around a table they will find common concerns and, possibly, common solutions, even if it seems they have contrasting views.
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of actors coming together to discuss issues was underlined; • Some of the concepts expressed: co-creation, multi-actor approach, peer to peer learning, collaborations between different ministries (i.e., agriculture and education), collaborations between AKIS actors; • The importance of the advisory system, and the need to improve it; • Skills: economic-financial (entrepreneurship) are missing in young farmers; read and interpret the market is missing too (both young and less young farmers);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For the design of the curricula, and to meet the needs of the sector, the need to adopt long-term thinking, and to see beyond the current or the future CAP;
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Field	Input
Event title	2nd Newsletter editorial board meeting
Type	Wp6 meeting
Place	Online meeting
Dates	March 4, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Creation of the final version of the internal NextFOOD newsletter Issue 7/2021
Relevance to the project	Creation and publication of an internal newsletter, dissemination of information about the project among the partners
Type of audience	Newsletter working group, internal researchers of the project (WP6)
Estimated size of targeted audience	6 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	BIOINSTITUT, UCH, ACRCM, ISEKI, SLU

Field	Input
Event title	METRIK seminar
Type	Seminar in the research groups 'METRIK' at Roskilde University and the Dean of the department 'Technology and Health Sciences'
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	March 08, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To present the scope, aim and preliminary results of the NF project with a particular focus on WP1 and a roadmap for the final year, and receive feedback from relevant researchers.
Relevance to the project	The event supported awareness of the NF project, dissemination of preliminary results and feedback from relevant researchers.
Type of audience	Researchers within the fields of food studies, agro-ecology, sustainable production and education and the Dean of the department 'Technology and Health Sciences'
Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Geographical scope of event	Regional/ National
Partner(s) involved	Stine Rosenlund Hansen Laura Sørensen Niels Heine Kristensen- RUC

Goal of presence	To present the NF project, preliminary results and future plans focusing on WP1, and receive feedback.
Feedback from the audience	The participants expressed that the presented results, ideas and plans were highly interesting and relevant.

Field	Input
Event title	Midtvejsseminar (Midterm seminar), Laura Sørensen
Type	Presentation of preliminary results and research process of NextFOOD PhD student Laura Sørensen
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	March 11, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To present the preliminary results of the PhD project, the roadmap for the final year, and receive feedback from relevant researchers.
Relevance to the project	The PhD project is part of the NF project and the event supported awareness of the NF project, dissemination of preliminary results and feedback from relevant researchers not involved with the NF project.
Type of audience	Researchers and PhD students within the fields of food studies, agro-ecology, sustainable production and education.
Estimated size of targeted audience	15
Geographical scope of event	Participants from Denmark and Norway.
Partner(s) involved	Laura Sørensen, Niels Heine Kristensen, Stine Rosenlund Hansen - RUC
Goal of presence	To organize the event, present preliminary results and future plans, and receive feedback.
Feedback from the audience	The participants expressed that the presented results, ideas and plans were highly interesting and relevant.

Field	Input
Place	Virtual meeting on Zoom
Dates	March 11, 2021
Stakeholder/Multiplier	Multiplayer meeting
Name	Synergy among LIAISON and NEXT FOOD project
Participants	<p>Susanne von Münchhausen, Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development (Germany): Susanne.vonMuenchhausen@hnee.de</p> <p>Mark Redman, Highclere Consulting (Romania): mark@highclere-consulting.com</p> <p>Dona Pickard, INSTITUTE FOR THE STUDY OF SOCIETIES AND KNOWLEDGE (Bulgaria): dona.pickard@gmail.com</p> <p>Elena Kopanarova and Daphne Kapsala (ACRCM)</p>
Position	<p>The aim of the meeting was the explore the opportunities for cooperation among the two Horizon projects in terms of exchange of good practices, promotion of deliverables and interaction in the scientific implementation of their work. The LIAISON project aims to make contribution to optimizing interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of EU policies to seed up innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. They were very interested to cooperate with NEXT FOOD projects in different levels as discussed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation or dissemination of their focus groups planned for the next week. Those will be promoted to the AFS and other local partners/universities. • Promotion of their event at social media • Structuring a meeting with the research team and project manager
Expected outreach	The LIAISON is aiming at interaction with education but is not going further in this point, which they expected to be covered by NEXT FOOD project. They are very interested in sharing questionnaires with our focus groups.
Results	We consider that fruitful cooperation can be set with this project and specific activities can be presented. They have already involved the project in their website: Related Projects and Networks LIAISON2020 https://liaison2020.eu/our-network/related-projects/

steps in our cooperation:

- Sharing the details of the project (PPT about their current process) with all the partners.
- Including more information about them at our next newsletter
- Sperate introduction to NF Project Coordinator and arrangement of meeting with the participation of the project manager of NEXT food
- Participation in roundtable for education in June 2021

Field	Input
Event Title	Synergy among RUBIZMO and NextFOOD
Place	Microsoft Teams, 15:00 CET
Dates	March 16, 2021
Stakeholder/Multiplier	Multiplayer meeting
Participants	Martin Melin Justin Casimir (RISE Sweden Research Institutes of Sweden AB) Daphne Kapsala (ACRCM) Elena Kopanarova (ACRCM) Apostolina Tsaltampasi (ACRCM))
Position	The aim of the meeting was the explore the opportunities for cooperation among the two Horizon projects in terms of exchange of good practices, promotion of deliverables and interaction in the scientific implementation of their work. RUBIZMO identify business models with high potential for empowering rural communities to take advantage of the opportunities arising from improved value chain optimization. RUBIZMO

	<p>have created the following results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual Library of business cases and practices (Business Tool 1) • Guidelines for support the business environment (Business Tool 2) • Supply tool for improving collaboration (Business Tool 3) • Online transformation tool (Business Tool 4) • Online educational materials (Master class modules)
Expected outreach	<p>The synergy with RUBIZMO is expected to affect the business orientation and specifically the case studies and the work delivers by SEKEM Development Foundation (Case study 10), University of Oradea (Case study 2) and Welthungerhilfe (Case study 9).</p>
Results	<p>Next steps in our cooperation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RUBIZMO is planning on 23rd March - VIRTUAL STUDY VISIT in Pomacle-Bazancourt biorefinery: a major center of European bioeconomy. The interested partners can register here: https://rise.zoom.us/meeting/register/u5Eld-6pqj0sGtZPZM5kKtWyIXMy7RJntJZE • RUBIZMO will invite NEXT FOOD experts to participate in the RUBIZMO Café Talks in April and May 2021. • RUBIZMO is interested to coach entrepreneurs from rural area and willing to promote this activity though NEXT FOOD project • RUBIZMO is going to invite our project manager at the final event of this project at October 2021.
	<p>Specifically, we have been invited to participate in the April Sessions of RUBIZMO Café talks & virtual visits (<i>see more details attached</i>) with topic <i>“Carbon, issue or added value for agriculture and rural areas”</i>. A series of quick and easy to access 30-minute “Café sessions” and virtual visits is taking place every Tuesday 11-11:30 CET as presented below:</p> <p>-13th April- VIRTUAL STUDY VISIT - Ecosystem Services (1h30 hours) by Dunhill Ekopark (Ireland) and Barycz Valley (Poland)</p>

	-20th April - Ola Petersson, RISE - Fossil free energy solutions of today and tomorrow -27th April - Tora Råberg, RISE - What is biochar and how to use it?
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Field	Input
Event title	Meeting/Workshop
Type	Meeting between Danish researchers and municipal actors involved with Horizon 2020 projects.
Place	Online
Dates	March 15, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To present the scope, aim and preliminary results of four Horizon 2020 projects and discuss potential knowledge-exchange and collaborations.
Relevance to the project	The event supported awareness of the NF project, dissemination of preliminary results, feedback from relevant researchers and new potential relations.
Type of audience	Researchers and municipal actors within the fields of food studies, food policy, sustainable design and production, LCA analysis and higher education.
Estimated size of targeted audience	6
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Stine Rosenlund Hansen, Niels Heine Kristensen – RUC
Goal of presence	To present the NF project, preliminary results and future plans focusing on WP1, receive feedback and establish new relevant networks.
Feedback from the audience	The participants expressed that the presented results, ideas and plans were highly interesting and relevant.

Field	Input
Event title	NextFOOD Dissemination Team Meeting
Type	Wp6 meeting
Place	Online meeting
Dates	March 26, 2021

Event aim & purpose	Package's progress, challenges and suggestions for improvement.
Relevance to the project	Creation and publication of an internal newsletter, dissemination of information about the project among the partners
Type of audience	Martin Melin (SLU), Maria Soumelidou (AFS), Line Friis Lindner (ISEKI), Alena Popelkova (BIOINSTITUT), Daphne Kapsala (ACRCM) and Dimitris Moustakis (AFS)
Estimated size of targeted audience	6 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	AFS, ISEKI, BIOINSTITUT, ACRCM, ISEKI, SLU

3.1.12 April 2021

Type and number of events:

- Digital/Workshop (1)
- Digital Workshop/Synergy (1)
- Digital/Peer learning meeting (1)
- Series of focus groups (2020-2021)

Field	Input
Event Title	Synergy among NEFERTITI and NEXT FOOD project
Place	Microsoft Teams
Dates	April 1, 2021
Stakeholder/Multiplier	Multiplayer meeting
Participants	Adrien GUICHAOUA, ACTA FR Martin Melin Daphne Kapsala (ACRCM) Elena Kopanarova (ACRCM) Apostolina Tsaltampasi (ACRCM)
Position	The aim of the meeting was to explore the opportunities for cooperation among the two Horizon projects in terms of exchange of good practices, promotion of deliverables and interaction in the scientific implementation of their work. NEFERTITI is a unique project that establishes 10 interactive thematic networks and bring together 45 regional clusters (hubs) of demo-farmers and

	<p>the involved actors (advisors, NGOs, industry, education, researchers and policy makers) in 17 countries. NEFERTITI focuses on creating added value from the exchange of knowledge, actors, farmers and technical content over the networks in order to boost innovation uptake, to improve peer to peer learning and network connectivity between farms actors across Europe, thus contributing to a more competitive, sustainable and climate-smart agriculture.</p>
<p>Expected outreach</p>	<p>The synergy with NEFERTITI is expected to affect networking possibilities among the members of both projects.</p>
<p>Results</p>	<p>We consider that fruitful cooperation can be set with this project and specific activities can be presented. We have discussed the following possibilities for cooperation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing the details of the project (PPT about their current process) with all the partners. • Including more information about them at our next newsletter • To be involved in the steps of policy dialogue with EU Regions to match farmers and policy makers' interests in view of the networks sustainability.

Field	Input
<p>Event title</p>	<p>Quality assessment of practice-oriented research.</p>
<p>Type</p>	<p>Arrangements of a series of focus group interviews and personal interviews.</p>
<p>Place</p>	<p>Alnarp, Sweden. Mostly digital meetings</p>
<p>Dates</p>	<p>01/04/20 – 30/04/21</p>

Event aim & purpose	Data collection and testing of the NextFOOD framework for evaluating the quality of interactive innovation and practice-oriented research in the agri-food sector.
Relevance to the project	The evaluation of applied research outputs for practice should focus rather on their economic and social usefulness than on their scientific character (part of WP5).
Type of audience	Researchers, advisers, veterinarians, farmers, farmers' organisations, farmers' suppliers and service firms, etc.
Estimated size of targeted audience	25
Geographical scope of event	All respondents reside in Sweden or Denmark
Partner(s) involved	The NextFOOD partner arranging these events is the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Goal of presence	Data collection and framework testing.
Feedback from the audience	This event will continue throughout 2021.
Stakeholders engaged	No publication yet.

Field	Input
Event title	Cedefop's foresight study on the EGD implications on employment and skills for the agri-food sector
Type	Workshop online Invitation to Line Lindner to join the expert group to contribute to Cedefop's foresight study
Place	Online, Zoom
Dates	12 April 2022, 10-13.30 CEST
Event aim & purpose	CEDEFOP is running a skills foresight study in four sectors to identify the implications of the implementation of the European Green Deal on skills and jobs, as well as any linked implications for vocational education and training (VET) design and delivery. The agriculture and food manufacturing (agri-food) sector was selected as one of the four. The study aims to identify: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) the changes in employment (e.g. in occupational structure) and skills in the sector, ignited by the implementation of the European Green Deal and other key drivers of change and ii) the respective possibilities and challenges for up- and re-skilling needs of workers in this sector. <p>After attendance in the online workshop this will be followed by participation in a Delphi survey</p>

	(first wave in May and second wave in June) and attendance at the final/validation online workshop scheduled for the first week of September (date to be confirmed).
Relevance to the project	The findings from the NextFOOD Skills Inventory are part of the background report and the findings from the questionnaire in WP1 will be used for contribution.
Type of audience	Unknown
Estimated size of targeted audience	Unknown
Geographical scope of event	European
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association

Field	Input
Event title	Peer learning: Multi actor approach/online action learning
Type	Peer learning meeting (online)
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	April 9, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The objective of the peer learning meetings is to share experiences between cases and facilitate generation of new knowledge regarding action learning and action research. In this particular meeting, the case representatives discussed multi-actor involvement in the casework and how to implement action learning in an online setting.
Relevance to the project	Related to the work in the NextFOOD cases
Type of audience	WP2 partners and case contributors
Estimated size of targeted audience	10-20
Geographical scope of event	Consortium wide
Partner(s) involved	WP2 partners
Goal of presence	Enhanced understanding and experience sharing between cases
Feedback from the audience	N/A
Stakeholders engaged	Case contributors and facilitators

3.1.13 May 2021

Type and number of events:

- Online Workshop (1)
- Online Workshop/Synergy (2)
- Conference (1)

Field	Input
Event Title	RUBIZMO EU Projects Collaboration Meeting
Place	Microsoft Teams, 15:00 CET
Dates	May 17, 2021
Stakeholder/Multiplier	Multiplayer meeting organised by ACRCM and AFS
Name	Synergy among RUBIZMO, NEXT FOOD, PoliRURAL, Ruritage
Participants	<p>Projects attended: NextFOOD, PoliRURAL, Ruritage, RUBIZMO</p>
Position	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Following brief presentation (attached in email) on proposal for Summer School, a discussion took place. • It was reiterated that the topics for the Summer School presented are a starting point and can be changed or mixed up. • While some of the projects' tools are targeted at one particular set of stakeholders, they are all relevant for the Summer School as the focus will be on training and learning. • The Summer School is about making the various stakeholders; whether these are policy makers, farm advisors, business advisors, support agencies, educators, trainers, funding agencies etc., aware that these tools exist and equip them with the knowledge of how these tools can be used to support and enhance their work. • Need to think about who we want to target and who will use the tools. • Suggested each project to target or headhunt 5-10 potential users of their tools and invite them to participate in the Summer School. • As each session will last between 2 and 2.5 hours it is important that we use our time wisely. • The sessions may be more productive by sending material – details of the tools, links to the tools, any demonstration videos, to participants in advance of each session so they can become familiar with the tools, test them and have questions or feedback prepared coming to the session. • The session itself can then focus on why and how the tool will benefit them in their work and answer any questions they may have on using the tool.

- One way to approach the sessions could be to categorise the users of the tools into three categories and then match the tools that would best suit them into each category for e.g.
 - Policy makers and Business Environment user – what tools would these be most interested in?
 - Practical users such as Farm/Business advisors etc. and;
 - Educators, trainers and funders.
- The important thing to remember is who are the core user groups of your project and tools.

Next Steps:

- RUBIZMO will draft a template of how the sessions would work and welcome your input in this.

Since the meeting on Monday RUBIZMO had further ideas on what else could be included as part of the sessions

- Information with registration link to all three sessions/themes/topics – the participants can attend more than one session.
- With the registration confirmation send very brief material and link to websites of the consortiums/projects
- Hold introductory session
- Send information with login-details for trials
- Offer a café/support session (well-staffed!) to do hands-on trials or if they experience any difficulties accessing the material
- At beginning of the second session give brief summary of the first theme
- Repeat this process for each session.

Field	Input
Event title	Nordic STS conference 2021
Type	Presentation at conference
Place	Online
Dates	May 20, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Development of theoretical and empirical insights into STS and the future as a matter of collective concern.
Relevance to the project	Presentation of project aim and results – feedback, inspiration and network
Type of audience	Researchers and students

Estimated size of targeted audience	50
Geographical scope of event	international
Partner(s) involved	Roskilde University
Goal of presence	Presentation of project aim and results – feedback, inspiration and network
Feedback from the audience	Provided inspiration for similarities with other projects, theories, literature.
Stakeholders engaged	Researchers
	https://www.dasts.dk/?tribe_events=nordic-sts-conference-2021-sts-and-the-future-as-a-matter-of-collective-concern

Field	Input
Event title	Synergy of NEXT FOOD and LOC-FOOD
Type	Technical Meeting
Place	Thessaloniki Greece
Dates	May 21, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Memorandum of cooperation between ACRCM and IHU through their partnership in NextFOOD project.
Relevance to the project	LOC-FOOD and NEXT FOOD project explored ways in which the two projects can collaborate to promote regional foods and to help support the agri-food economy of the region and stressed the need for sustainable economic and social development in rural areas, with initiatives that include environmental, social and economic dimensions aimed at enhancing regional cooperation through the synergy of NextFOOD and LOC-FOOD projects.
Type of audience	Academians, Regional Consultants, Executive Staff
Estimated size of targeted audience	6
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM, IHU
Goal of presence	The aim of this collaboration is to identify agri-food products whose quality and interesting characteristics make them suitable candidates for certification under the European Union's quality scheme as Protected Designation of Origin (PDO), Protected Geographical Indication (PGI), or Traditional Speciality Guaranteed (TSG). This action forms part of the international project 'Local Development and Cross Border

	Cooperation in the area of Agricultural Products and Traditional Food' (acronym: LOC-FOOD), funded by the Joint Operational Programme Black Sea Basin 2014-2020, part of the EU's Black Sea Cross Border Cooperation Programme.
Feedback from the audience	The overall coordinator of the project is the Department of Co-funded Regional Development Programmes of the Ministry of the Interior (Sector Macedonia and Thrace). The coordinator at IHU is Professor Maria Papageorgiou of the Department of Food Science and Technology. ACRCM is contributing to the LOC-FOOD project through its role as informal partner to IHU
Stakeholders engaged	Useful links: <u>LOC FOOD project</u> <u>Food Science and Technology Department of the Internationnal Hellenic University of Thessaloniki, Greece</u> <u>Agronutritional Cooperation Region Central Macedonia</u>

Field	Input
Event title	Synergy between Rubizmo and NextFOOD
Type	Online meeting
Place	Romania (Oradea-Bucharest)
Dates	May 26, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To identify synergies between the two projects in discussion; to exchange information and materials developed in the two projects (e.g. Canvas), to find new forms of cooperation between the participants.
Relevance to the project	Dissemination/Sharing of the Nextfood results with other European projects
Type of audience	Academic staff, researchers, farmers, representatives of farmer associations
Estimated size of targeted audience	16
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	UNIOR, ACRCM ARAD association, partner within Rubizmo project University of Oradea, partner within NextFOOD Representatives of Crisana Association, Romanian Association for Sustainable Agriculture
Goal of presence	The goal was to disseminate relevant information on the NextFOOD project, to exchange materials developed within the two projects and to find

	new ways of cooperation even after the end of the two projects
Feedback from the audience	It was a successful meeting in which many initiatives have been taken into discussion.
Stakeholders engaged	<p>The ACRCM promoted a fruitful collaboration between two key partners:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. University of ORADEA, partner and leader of the Romanian Case of NextFOOD project: Students and farmers taking food innovations from idea to market: A practice-oriented course in food innovation including all the steps necessary to bring a new product to the market (Read more: https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-2-students-and-farmers-taking-food-innovations-from-idea-to-market/) and 2. ARAD Association partner of RUBIZMO project which developed "THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS "CAMELINA OMEGA 3 PLUS", "Agrarian Economy and Rural Development-Realities and Perspectives for Romania", (Read more: https://mpira.ub.uni-muenchen.de/106299/) <p>Apart of the dissemination of relevant information and the exchange of materials developed between the two projects the goal was the exploration of new ways of cooperation even after the end of the two projects on topics such as: biodynamic agriculture, viticulture, organic wines, bio-pesticides, local seeds bank.</p>
	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/synergy-of-the-university-of-oradea-and-arad-romanian-association-for-sustainable-agriculture-in-the-framework-of-horizon2020-projects-nextfood-and-rubizmo/

3.1.14 June 2021

Type and number of events:

- WP/Partners Meeting (1)
- Digital Conference (2)
- Peer learning meeting (online) (2)
- Webinar (1)
- Workshop (1)
- Partner's Conference (1)

Field	Input
Event title	3rd Newsletter editorial board meeting
Type	Wp6 meeting
Place	Online meeting
Dates	June 2, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Creation of the final version of the internal NextFOOD newsletter Issue 8/2021
Relevance to the project	Creation and publication of an internal newsletter, dissemination of information about the project among the partners
Type of audience	Newsletter working group, internal researchers of the project (WP6)
Estimated size of targeted audience	5 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	BIOINSTITUT, ACRCM, UCH, ISEKI, AFS

Field	Input
Event title	Workshop on the applications of precision technologies in olive trees
Type	Workshop
Place	Chalkidiki, Greece
Dates	June 3, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To enable students, apply their theoretical knowledge on precision technologies to a real-life olive farm.
Relevance to the project	To provide outlets of practical experience to students, connect students with real-economy actors, introduce sustainable practices to farmers, and to promote the significance of precision technologies in university curricula.
Type of audience	Postgraduate agricultural students, professors, farmers, and advisors

Estimated size of targeted audience	20 (in person)
Geographical scope of event	Regional
Partner(s) involved	AFS, IHU

Field	Input
Event title	Poster presentation of findings from the Greek NextFOOD case at the 25th European Seminar on Extension and Education (ESEE 2021)
Type	Conference Participation
Place	Cavan, Ireland
Dates	June 21-23, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To present the most recent developments related to agricultural extension and education.
Relevance to the project	Preliminary findings from the Greek NextFOOD case were presented to a varied audience of agri-food professionals, policy makers and academics; contributing thus the dissemination of project outputs.
Type of audience	Agri-food professionals, policy makers, academics
Estimated size of targeted audience	500 (online)
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	AFS
Goal of presence	To communicate and disseminate findings from the NextFOOD project to a diverse group of stakeholders and interested parties.
Stakeholders engaged	https://esee2021.ie/

The online learning experience: Undergraduate students' perceptions on the online course delivery

George Zahitos¹, Eleni Papadopoulou², Aristidis Lyberopoulos^{3*}

Background

Research interest in growing is identifying the challenges and factors that can promote the successful delivery of action-based online courses.^{1,4}

The current study fills an identified need for exploring Greek agricultural students' perceptions on and experiences of online learning utilizing action-based activities during the COVID-19 outbreak.

This study was undertaken as part of NextFOOD, a Horizon 2020 funded research programme aiming to educate and support budding or already practicing professionals on the development of competences in order to push the green agenda in our rapidly changing society.

Aim

To explore students' perceptions on and experiences of the online delivery of the course "Farm Animal Reproduction".

Methodology

Participants: undergraduate agricultural students were involved in action-based learning activities aiming at their active involvement and engagement in the educational process.

Data collection: 8 online focus groups (8 participants per group), lasting 45-60 minutes. Group discussions were audio recorded and, subsequently, transcribed verbatim.

Data Analysis: thematic analysis with the assistance of the ATLAS.ti software was used to identify common patterns and themes in the data.

Main findings

Thematic analysis revealed a number of codes and subcodes that were grouped into three main themes: 1. Challenges, 2. Positive aspects, and 3. Recommendations.

"I am not very fan of the online course. We had lots for 2 hours and the professor just repeated the slides only to answer our questions. After the hour I could not attend the next lesson because of my schedule. It was difficult for me to keep my concentration for 2 hours. It would have been comfortable with the teacher and the other group members because we could not see each other. However, we did not have the opportunity to meet face-to-face. Personally, I don't like the online course". Student, Female, 18-22

"I have to say that I had difficulties in the online course because I live at a village. So, the electricity was cut off quite often. Therefore, I was prevented for one subject of the course. I also had problems with my internet connection. So, it was difficult for me to attend and be able to collect the information that I needed". Student, Male, 18-22

"I would say that having the course online is not convenient for me. I did not have to travel to get to the University, I stayed at the convenience of my house. Having to travel to get to the University costs me a lot of time. I have needed to move three days this year. It's like a gift!". Student, Female, 18-22

"Teachers need to encourage the active participation of the students and create the opportunity for more communication and group working. For example, teachers could group members into discussion through questions and answers. In the face-to-face interaction we know the teacher's opinion. That is not the case in the online course. It is very difficult for us to ask questions. It is slow when we are in a discussion". Student, Female, 18-22

"We needed more practice and more time in order to divide the things we have to do in a group. Searching for information for our topic was a difficult task. However, we were searching at the same information and there was not to include the entire information. We also had to split our topic in manageable subtopics. That was something new and difficult for us to do. We need to find ways to divide the things, so each group member will know what to do. Discussion and setting a group moderator could be a solution. It was hard for us to find a solution. We didn't have these experiences". Student, Female, 18-22

Conclusion

Action-based online courses in agriculture can provide great potential for educational programmes.

More research is needed to identify factors relating to the successful delivery of online courses incorporating action-based learning activities and technologies.

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Abbreviations

1. Strategic Planning Management Office, American College of Greece

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Keywords: NextFOOD, online learning, action-based learning, agricultural students, COVID-19, Greece

Intentional Hellenic University **American Farm School**
Thessaloniki, Greece

Field	Input
Event title	Impact of European programmes in the Reinforcement of the competitiveness and extroversion of SMEs
Type	Online Webinar
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	June 2, 2021
Event aim & purpose	ACRCM participated in the 13 th Education Festival 2021-the greatest teacher festival in Greece and Europe powered by IEK ALPHA & MEDITERRANEAN COLLEGE, which was organized from 1 st of March to 4 th of June 2021.
Relevance to the project	The students of The Rural Development Department of IEK ALPHA within the Education Festival 2021 participated in a Free Webinar entitled "Impact of European programmes in the Reinforcement of the competitiveness and extroversion of SMEs". The timelessness of Education and the "revolutionary" changes of its methods, like the virtual reality in the educational process today, was the major topic the 13th EDUCATION FESTIVAL. The President of

	ACRCM, Mr. Konstantinos Kiltidis, presented on the effects of the implementation of European projects in the Reinforcement of the competitiveness and extroversion of SMEs. Specifically, he introduced the NextFOOD project and its among 80 students of the Rural Development Department of IEK ALPHA.
Type of audience	Students and Professors of IEK ALPHA-MEDITERRANEAN COLLEGE
Estimated size of targeted audience	80
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM
Goal of presence	The agricultural sector is the basis of the productive dynamics of Greece. Greece's agricultural policy is shaped within the framework of the European Common Agricultural Policy. The importance of a common agricultural policy is essential for the sustainable development of the Greek agri-food sector.
Feedback from the audience	In accordance with the objectives of NextFOOD project "Educating the Next Generation of Professionals in the Agri-Food sector" it was pointed out the need of digital skills and digital literacy among professionals.
Stakeholders engaged	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rw5baBR2neo

Field	Input
Event title	ESEE 2021 – the 25th European Seminar on extension and education
Type	Scientific conference Participation
Place	Digital conference. Arranged from Teagasc Ballyhaise Agricultural College, Cava, Ireland.
Dates	June 21-23, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The European Seminar on Extension and Education (ESEE) is a group of educators and advisors who hold a biennial conference and publish a Journal on topics related to agricultural extension and education. Theme: Learning for life Continuous innovation support through extension and education for sustainable farm communities. Innovation is supported by the ongoing learning, actions and interactions of

	<p>individuals, groups and communities which result in better decisions and actions which are economically, socially and environmentally sustainable. Agricultural advisors and teachers are key enablers of this on-going learning environment.</p>
<p>Relevance to the project</p>	<p>The conference theme was “Learning for life”. A conference paper was presented, derived from the work with the NextFOOD project.</p>
<p>Type of audience</p>	<p>Researchers of agricultural knowledge and innovation systems, advisory service professionals etc.</p>
<p>Estimated size of targeted audience</p>	<p>Around 400 participants</p>
<p>Geographical scope of event</p>	<p>International</p>
<p>Partner(s) involved</p>	<p>Teagasc was the convenor. Many organisations took part. / SLU</p>
<p>Goal of presence</p>	<p>A conference paper was presented, derived from the work with the NextFOOD project</p>
<p>Feedback from the audience</p>	<p>Questions and comments on the presentation</p>
<p>Stakeholders engaged</p>	<p>ESEE 2021 25th European Seminar on Extension & Education 21-23 June 2021</p>

Field	Input
<p>Event title</p>	<p>6th ISEKI-Food Conference</p>
<p>Type</p>	<p>Conference</p>
<p>Place</p>	<p>Online</p>
<p>Dates</p>	<p>23/06/2021-25/06/2021</p>
<p>Event aim & purpose</p>	<p>Conference title: “Sustainable Development Goals in Food Systems – Challenges and Opportunities for the Future”</p>
<p>Relevance to the project</p>	<p>Line Lindner gave an oral presentation on “Facilitator Reflection on online Action-learning “ in the EDUCATION SESSION: Facing challenges in education for a globalised and sustainable world held Monday 23 June 2021. And Christoph Knöbl gave a poster presentation on “Changed learner experiences after action learning”. Both abstracts were prepared together with Katherine Flynn.</p>
<p>Type of audience</p>	<p>Teachers in HE</p>
<p>Estimated size of targeted audience</p>	<p>170 participants from 39 countries</p>
<p>Geographical scope of event</p>	<p>International</p>
<p>Partner(s) involved</p>	<p>ISEKI-Food Association: Line Lindner, Christoph Knöbl, Katherine Flynn</p>

Goal of presence	To present the oral and poster presentation
Feedback from the audience	
Stakeholders engaged	Publications (isekiconferences.com)

Field	Input
Event title	Peer learning: Exploring ward to organize and categorize data in NVivo
Type	Peer learning meeting (online)
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	June 23, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The objective of the peer learning meetings is to share experiences between cases and facilitate generation of new knowledge regarding action learning and action research. In this meeting WP2 leader (NMBU) conducted a presentation of the qualitative data analysis software NVivo and how to optimize the use of its different features.
Relevance to the project	Related to the work in the NextFOOD cases
Type of audience	WP2 partners and case contributors
Estimated size of targeted audience	10-20
Geographical scope of event	Consortium wide
Partner(s) involved	WP2 partners
Goal of presence	Enhanced understanding and experience sharing between cases
Stakeholders engaged	Case contributors and facilitators

Field	Input
Event title	Peer learning: Facilitating the multi-actor approach online
Type	Peer learning meeting (online)
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	June 29, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The objective of the peer learning meetings is to share experiences between cases and facilitate generation of new knowledge regarding action learning and action research. In this meeting, the case representatives discussed multi-actor involvement in the casework and how to implement action learning in an online setting.
Relevance to the project	Related to the work in the NextFOOD cases
Type of audience	WP2 partners and case contributors
Estimated size of targeted audience	10-20
Geographical scope of event	Consortium wide
Partner(s) involved	WP2 partners

Goal of presence	Enhanced understanding and experience sharing between cases
Feedback from the audience	N/A
Stakeholders engaged	Case contributors and facilitators

<p>Partners' Conference 04 – 25 May 2021 Program</p> <hr/> <p>4th of May, 13-15 WP7 – Catching-up and plans for the final year in NextFOOD. Info about technical and financial reports.</p> <p>5th of May, 13-15 WP5- Research impact assessment framework, preliminary results from the three pilots in Sweden, Czech Republic and Greece</p> <p>7th of May, 13-15 WP1 – The identified gaps in research and education, preliminary findings from the informatics project and the research needs survey.</p> <p>11th of May, 13-15 WP1 – The updated inventory of skills, preliminary findings from the skills survey and the audit tool.</p> <p>12th of May, 13-15 WP2 – The development of the educational cases</p> <p>18th of May, 13-15 WP3- An updated version of the NextFOOD educational system</p> <p>24th of May, 13-15 WP4 – Development of policy instruments in agri-food and forestry education, recent results and next steps</p> <p>25th of May, 13-14 WP6 – Dissemination plan for the final year</p> <p>25th of May, 14-15 WP7- Wrap-up session</p>
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All the presentation are available here:

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-Mb1MaYOrFV4owhLQzJ

3.1.15 July 2021

Type and number of events:

- WP/Partners Meetings/digital (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Toolbox workshop
Type	Online workshop (WP2&WP6)
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	July 29, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of this workshop was to make the Toolbox more useful and user-friendly. We invited all WP2 case leaders and researchers to a workshop to get feedback on content and layout. We also invited the communications/IT-team who work with the practical functioning of the

	<p>toolbox in the NextFOOD platform, to participate with their expert knowledge on possibilities for the toolbox development.</p> <p>We asked the WP2 case leaders and researcher to explore the toolbox in the NextFOOD platform, and reflect upon the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do you find using the toolbox? • What do you like about the toolbox the way it is today? • What do you think is missing, and what are your suggestions for improvement?
Relevance to the project	Related to the work on the NextFOOD Toolbox – an important outcome of the project
Type of audience	WP2 partners, case contributors, communications/IT
Estimated size of targeted audience	10-20
Geographical scope of event	Consortium wide
Partner(s) involved	NMBU, WP2 partners, ACRCM
Goal of presence	Feedback on and improvement of the NextFOOD Toolbox
Feedback from the audience	Relevant feedback on the Toolbox was given both during the workshop and in written form
Stakeholders engaged	Case contributors and facilitators

3.1.16 August 2021

Type and number of events:

- WP/Partners meeting/digital (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Toolbox follow-up workshop
Type	Online workshop (WP2 & WP6)
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	August 30, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of this set of workshops was to make the Toolbox more useful and user-friendly. We invited all WP2 case leaders and researchers to a workshop to get feedback on content and layout. We also invited the communications/IT-team who work with the practical functioning of the toolbox in the NextFOOD platform, to participate with their expert knowledge on possibilities for the toolbox development.

	This workshop was arranged to follow-up on the previous meeting from July 2021, and the purpose was to collect feedback on the changes made.
Relevance to the project	Related to the work on the NextFOOD Toolbox – an important outcome of the project
Type of audience	WP2 partners, case contributors, communications/IT
Estimated size of targeted audience	10-20
Geographical scope of event	Consortium wide
Partner(s) involved	WP2 partners, NMBU, ACRCM, AFS
Goal of presence	Feedback on and improvement of the NextFOOD Toolbox
Feedback from the audience	Relevant feedback on the Toolbox was given both during the workshop and in written form
Stakeholders engaged	Case contributors and facilitators

3.1.17 September 2021

Type and number of events:

- WP/Partners meeting (1)
- WP/Partners meeting/digital (1)
- Workshop (1)
- Workshop and training (1)
- Forum (1)

Field	Input
Event title	NextFOOD Entrepreneurship Program 2021 – Cycle 1 Start-up projects
Type	Workshop and training at Sekem Farm, Belbeis, Sharkia governorate, Egypt. Participation of Sekem development foundation - Faculty of Organic Agriculture, Heliopolis University - Entrepreneurship Center for Social Impact, Heliopolis University – EBDA (Egyptian biodynamic Association)
Place	Sharkia governorate, Egypt
Dates	5 days of training (10/09/2021 to 11/09/2021) (17/09/2021 to 19/09/2021)

Event aim & purpose	Introduce the participants to Bio-fertilizers, Compost production, IPM strategies, Organic Agriculture aspects, Bio-pesticide, Horticulture production such citrus, and Animal Livestock Husbandry. In addition to topics of Marketing, Finance, Business model canvas, and feasibility study for business development.
Relevance to the project	Achieving the objectives of the NextFOOD project to develop and improve the skills of participants of young start up leaders and cover the main 5 core competences of learning.
Type of audience	They were different categories of housewives, fresh graduated, students of Organic Agriculture and small business owners.
Estimated size of targeted audience	20 participants
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Sekem development foundation - Faculty of Organic Agriculture, Heliopolis University - Entrepreneurship Center for Social Impact, Heliopolis University)
Goal of presence	Follow the training process closely and participate in some sessions
Feedback from the audience	It was successful training that clarified many business topics related to how to run their own small projects

Field	Input
Event title	Oral presentation of findings from the Greek NextFOOD case at the PROPEDIA forum
Type	Forum Participation
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	September 13, 2021

Event aim & purpose	To discuss the parameters needed for agri-food businesses to remain competitive. The event was hosted on 13.09.2021 at The International Exhibition Center of Thessaloniki in the context of the 85th Thessaloniki International Fair and focus was on the connection of education and research with the agro- business sector.
Relevance to the project	Preliminary findings from the Greek NextFOOD case were presented to a varied audience of agri-food professionals, policy makers and academics; contributing thus the dissemination of project outputs.
Type of audience	Agri-food professionals, policy makers, academics, Dr. Filippos Papadopoulos from the AFS presented NextFOOD findings informing the agenda of the newly established industry-academia think tank "Propaedia".
Estimated size of targeted audience	150 (50 in person, 100 online)
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	AFS, ACRCM
Goal of presence	To communicate and disseminate findings from the NextFOOD project to a diverse group of stakeholders and interested parties.
Stakeholders engaged	http://prwpaideia.eu/wp/2021/08/28/917/

Field	Input
Event title	4th Newsletter editorial board meeting
Type	WP6 Meeting
Place	Online meeting
Dates	September 14, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Creation of the final version of the internal NextFOOD newsletter Issue 9/2021

Relevance to the project	Creation and publication of an internal newsletter, dissemination of information about the project among the partners
Type of audience	Newsletter working group, internal researchers of the project (WP6)
Estimated size of targeted audience	3 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM, BIOINSTITUT

Field

Event Title

Input

Skogforsk case – meeting
Forest management and preservation at the same time – is this possible?

Type	Educational meeting / workshop Organization
Place	Experimental forest site - Bredvik, Sweden
Dates	September 16, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Skogforsk is running a case aiming at a higher understanding about logging techniques, strategies, and methods to increase quality and number of micro-habitats in production forests. Educational meeting and workshop together with a group of private forest owners all having an interest in forest management and preservation.
Relevance to the project	WP 2 Case study – private forest owners. We will develop the NextFOOD model to also work for private individuals and forestry officials who sometimes have limited resources in time and commitment.
Type of audience	Private forest owners who have an interest in alternative methods of forestry. Officials who wish to broaden their knowledge around microhabitats. Researchers who want to learn more about the complex issue of forestry
Estimated size of targeted audience	Participants at this meeting – 9 forest owners and the Skogforsk NextFOOD-team
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	Education and action research
Feedback from the audience	“Super exciting discussions.” “Difficult questions that have many answers.” “Good forum to learn more.” “More time in the forest to have a dialogue about various dilemmas”

Stakeholders engaged	Private forest owners that are members of a forest owners association in the middle of Sweden.
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Field	Input
Event title	WP1 meeting regarding the further advancement of D1.2
Type	Work Meeting (LU is responsible for coordinating the work regarding the development of an online audit tool based on D1.2 – Audit tool for research and education. The meeting was held in this context)
Place	Online
Dates	September 29, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of the event was to determine next steps regarding the development of an online tool for educators based on D1.2
Relevance to the project	The meeting opens for initiating a process of turning D1.2 into a useful and practical self-assessment tool for educators internationally.
Type of audience	Representatives of WP5 partners LU, RUC, SLU
Estimated size of targeted audience	5
Geographical scope of event	Sweden
Partner(s) involved	LU, RUC, SLU
Goal of presence	The event is an important milestone in the optimization and dissemination of D1.2 in WP1

3.1.18 October 2021

Type and number of events:

- WP/Partners meeting / Cases (8)
- Peer learning meeting (online) (3)
- Training Course (2)
- Workshops (2)
- Dissemination event (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Skogforsk case – meeting Forest management and preservation at the same time – is this possible?
Type	Educational meeting / workshop Organization
Place	Private forest estate - Stavby, Sweden
Dates	October 6, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Skogforsk is running a case aiming at a higher understanding about logging techniques, strategies, and methods to increase quality and number of micro-habitats in production forests. Educational meeting and workshop together with a group of private forest owners all having an interest in forest management and preservation.
Relevance to the project	WP 2 Case study – we will develop the NextFOOD model to also work for private individuals and forestry officials who sometimes have limited resources in time and commitment.
Type of audience	Private forest owners who have an interest in alternative methods of forestry. Officials who wish to broaden their knowledge around microhabitats. Researchers who want to learn more about the complex issue of forestry
Estimated size of targeted audience	Participants – 9 forest owners, 1 forestry official and the Skogforsk NextFOOD-team
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	Education and action research
Feedback from the audience	“Super exciting discussions.” “Difficult questions that have many answers.” “Good forum to learn more.” “More time in the forest to have a dialogue about various dilemmas”

Stakeholders engaged

Private forest owners that are members of a forest owners association in the middle of Sweden and forestry officials working at this organisation

Field	Input
Event title	WP2 case workshops
Type	Meeting with WP2-leader and cases
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	18/10/2021 (SEKEM); 19/10/2021 (UCH); 20/10/2021 (ISEKI); 21/10/2021 (AFS); 22/10/2021 (USB); 25/10/2021 (UoK); 28/10/2021 (Skogforsk); 29/10/2021 (UNIOR; UoC); 02/11/2021 (CIHEAM)
Event aim & purpose	The aim of the meetings is to provide detailed, individual feedback on the cases' last Case development report as well as to follow up on the action research activities to be conducted in the cases in the final NextFOOD year.
Relevance to the project	Related to the WP2 casework
Type of audience	Case contributors and leaders
Estimated size of targeted audience	3-10
Geographical scope of event	N/A
Partner(s) involved	WP2 partners
Goal of presence	Case development report feedback and case development

WP2 ACTION RESEARCH FACILITATION

Field	Input
Event title	Opening event of EUPHORIA project.
Type	Event (dissemination)
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	October 14, 2021
Event aim & purpose	NextFOOD project was presented during the opening event of EUPHORIA project.
Relevance to the project	During the event the President of ACRCM, Konstantinos Kiltidis presented the mission of NextFOOD project to the stakeholders and the significance of an agricultural educational strategy which will shrink the gap between research, education, and farming and will bring together students, academics, and advisors to practice farming in accordance to guidelines for sustainable farming techniques.
Type of audience	Stakeholders, producers, journalists, regional consultants of RCM, academics, representatives of AFS and IHU
Estimated size of targeted audience	50
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM
Goal of presence	The present action EUPHORIA aims to enhance the competitiveness of specific product categories PDO/PGI of the regional agri-food sector targeting the internal market and to improve the perception on food safety and traceability for the escalation of high quality and nutritional value products based on the <i>EU's common agricultural policies</i> .
Feedback from the audience	The project expectations are the reinforcement of shortcomings of policies related to agri-food and forestry education in the EU which will insure the enhancement of the employment, to increase the income of the producer and entrepreneur, as well as enhancing the quality of life of the people.

Stakeholders engaged	https://euphoriaproject.eu/index.php/nea/event/PortoPalace.html
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Field	Input
Event title	Peer learning: D3.5 Report on Educational Strategy – Thoughts sharing
Type	Peer learning meeting (online)
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	October 13, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The objective of the peer learning meetings is to share experiences between cases and facilitate generation of new knowledge regarding action learning and action research. In this meeting, the case representatives discussed the main findings from cross-case analysis based on the past cycle's data. This meeting's purpose was to get more insight in what cases wanted to focus on or learn more about during the action research in the ongoing or coming cycle.
Relevance to the project	Related to the work in the NextFOOD cases
Type of audience	WP2 partners and case contributors
Estimated size of targeted audience	10-20
Geographical scope of event	Consortium wide
Partner(s) involved	WP2 partners
Goal of presence	Enhanced understanding and experience sharing between cases
Feedback from the audience	N/A
Stakeholders engaged	Case contributors and facilitators

Field	Input
Event title	NextFOOD Entrepreneurship Program 2021 – Cycle 2 //Start-up projects
Type	Workshop and training at Entrepreneurship Center for Social Impact
Place	Cairo, Egypt
Dates	October 15-17, 2021 The final pitch day on 24th October 2021
Event aim & purpose	Introduce the participants to different business topics Marketing, sales, leadership skills and project management for their business development.
Relevance to the project	Achieving the objectives of the NextFOOD project to develop and improve the skills of participants

	of young start up leaders and cover the main 5 core competences of learning.
Type of audience	They were different categories of housewives, fresh graduated, students of Organic Agriculture and small business owners. In this cycle, the number of small business owners. Had been increased.
Estimated size of targeted audience	21 participants
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Sekem development foundation - Faculty of Organic Agriculture, Heliopolis University - Entrepreneurship Center for Social Impact, Heliopolis University)
Goal of presence	Follow the training process closely and contribute to sessions related with NextFOOD approaches of learning
Stakeholders engaged	Successful and fruitful training covered many business topics related to how to run their own small projects

Field	Input
Event title	Biodynamic Training Course
Type	Biodynamic Training Course at Sekem Farm, Belbeis, Sharkia governorate, Egypt. Training for two weeks in the field with Organic Agriculture students Heliopolis university. Participation of OA students, and organised by professors and TAs of faculty of organic Agriculture, Heliopolis university. The training includes different visits to Adlya Farm and El-Mizan belong to Sekem farm in addition to different factories such as ISIS, Naturetex, and Lotus.
Place	Sharkia governorate, Egypt
Dates	October 17- 28, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Introduce the students to principles of biodynamic, organic agriculture, soil structure,

	soil fertility, compost production and the effect of different factors on soil formation.
Relevance to the project	Achieving the objectives of the NextFOOD project to develop and improve the skills of educators of young students and cover the main 5 core competences of learning.
Type of audience	Fresh undergraduate students of organic agriculture faculty, Heliopolis University.
Estimated size of targeted audience	61 students
Geographical scope of event	local
Partner(s) involved	Helipolis University – Sekem farm in cooperation with Adlya Farm and El-Mizan belong to Sekem farm in addition to different factories such as ISIS, Naturetex, and Lotus.
Goal of presence	Follow the training process closely
Feedback from the audience	Introduce the students to different kind of teaching methodology from outside class to real life and dealing with nature in open field.
	Photos below taken by: Salma Nour El-Deen Event Reporting: Reham Fathey Ali

Field	Input
Event title	Peer learning: NextFOOD approach
Type	Peer learning meeting (online)
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	October 20, 2021

Event aim & purpose	The objective of the peer learning meetings is to share experiences between cases and facilitate generation of new knowledge regarding action learning and action research. In this meeting, the case representatives discussed what to consider when converting or starting up a course in line with the NextFOOD approach. This meeting's purpose was to get more insight in what the cases found difficult or easy in case development.
Relevance to the project	Related to the work in the NextFOOD cases
Type of audience	WP2 partners and case contributors
Estimated size of targeted audience	10-20
Geographical scope of event	Consortium wide
Partner(s) involved	WP2 partners
Goal of presence	Enhanced understanding and experience sharing between cases
Feedback from the audience	N/A
Stakeholders engaged	Case contributors and facilitators

Field	Input
Event title	Meeting of WP5 partners regarding the final deliverable – ready to use peer review system
Type	WP5 Meeting (LU is responsible for coordinating the work regarding the final deliverable. The meeting was held in this context)
Place	Online
Dates	October 21, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of the event was to establish and delimit the roles of each participating WP5 partner in the work towards the final deliverable in this work package. Next steps were determined.
Relevance to the project	The meeting brings the WP5 partners together to jointly establish the overall structure and content of the final deliverable.
Type of audience	Representatives of the WP5 project partners
Estimated size of targeted audience	8
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	LU, SLU, AFS, USB
Goal of presence	The event is an important milestone in the finalisation of the final deliverable in WP5

Field	Input
Event title	Workshop on the use of the goal setting tool programme for IHU students
Type	Workshop Organization
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	October 25, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To introduce the goal setting tool to students and university professors, and motivate them to participate in the programme.
Relevance to the project	To offer an additional tool to agricultural students that aims to enhance academic motivation, the competence of reflection and personal development.
Type of audience	Agricultural students and professors
Estimated size of targeted audience	300 (in person)
Geographical scope of event	Regional
Partner(s) involved	AFS, IHU

Field	Input
Event title	Peer learning: Facilitation
Type	Peer learning meeting (online)
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	October 27, 2021
Event aim & purpose	<p>The objective of the peer learning meetings is to share experiences between cases and facilitate generation of new knowledge regarding action learning and action research. In this meeting, the case representatives discussed multi-actor involvement in the casework and how to implement action learning in an online setting.</p> <p>This meeting's purpose was to exchange experiences on the shift from lecturer to learning facilitator, and to identify supporting and</p>

	hindering forces, how to build on the supporting and overcome the hindering.
Relevance to the project	Related to the work in the NextFOOD cases
Type of audience	WP2 partners and case contributors
Estimated size of targeted audience	10-20
Geographical scope of event	Consortium wide
Partner(s) involved	NMBU, WP2 partners
Goal of presence	Enhanced understanding and experience sharing between cases
Feedback from the audience	N/A
Stakeholders engaged	Case contributors and facilitators

3.1.19 November 2021

Type and number of events:

- Conference (1)
- One Month Certificate Course (1)
- Workshop (3)
- Workshop/Case (1)
- Hybrid Workshop/Dissemination event (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Food education and STEM teaching
Type	Organization and participation of meeting
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	November 11, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To explore opportunities for collaboration between the organisation Vibevadgaard and Roskilde University with regards to education in Food education, STEM teaching and Food systems.
Relevance to the project	Feedback and dissemination
Type of audience	Educational practitioners, farmer, researcher
Estimated size of targeted audience	7
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Roskilde University
Goal of presence	Explore opportunities for collaborations
Feedback from the audience	Lessons learned in the NextFOOD project comes in very helpful to this regional food initiative.
Stakeholders engaged	Educational practitioners, farmer, researcher

Field	Input
Event title	GRASP conference – A festival of new ideas
Type	Conference presentation
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	November 18, 2021
Event aim & purpose	GRASP is a festival that seeks to explore some of the most burning issues of our time – sustainable development across disciplines, urban development through research, music, activism and art and communities in the wake of the pandemic
Relevance to the project	Presentation of project aim and results – feedback, inspiration and network.
Type of audience	Researchers, practitioners, artists, activists, students
Estimated size of targeted audience	45
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Roskilde University
Goal of presence	Presentation of project aim and results – feedback, inspiration and network
Feedback from the audience	Provided inspiration for similarities with other projects, theories, literature.
Stakeholders engaged	https://graspfestival.dk/

Field	Input
Event title	Meeting with Nordic Center for Local Food
Type	Workshop /Participation
Place	Nykøbing Sjælland, Denmark
Dates	November 17, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Workshop on development of educational program on sustainable, local food as part of developing a new regional campus
Relevance to the project	Lessons learned in the NextFOOD project comes in very helpful to this regional food initiative.
Type of audience	Developers of food campus
Estimated size of targeted audience	3
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Niels Heine Kristensen, Roskilde University Stine Rosenlund Hansen, RUC
Goal of presence	Invited expert
Feedback from the audience	Common understanding for further cooperation
Stakeholders engaged	Consultant, advisors, regional planners

Field	Input
Event title	Skogforsk case – meeting Forest management and preservation at the same time – is this possible?
Type	Educational meeting / Workshop
Place	Private forest estate - Råda, Sweden
Dates	November 17, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Skogforsk is running a case aiming at a higher understanding about logging techniques, strategies, and methods to increase quality and number of micro-habitats in production forests. Educational meeting and workshop together with a group of private forest owners all having an interest in forest management and preservation.
Relevance to the project	WP 2 Case study – develop the model to also work for private individuals and forestry officials who sometimes have limited resources in time and commitment.
Type of audience	Private forest owners who have an interest in alternative methods of forestry. Officials who wish to broaden their knowledge around microhabitats. Researchers who want to learn more about the complex issue of forestry.
Estimated size of targeted audience	Participants – 9 forest owners, 2 forestry officials and the Skogforsk NextFOOD-team
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	Education and action research
Feedback from the audience	“Super exciting discussions.” “Difficult questions that have many answers.” “Good forum to learn more.” “More time in the forest to have a dialogue about various dilemmas”
Stakeholders engaged	Private forest owners that are members of a forest owners association in the middle of Sweden and forestry officials working at this organisation

Field	Input
Event Title	NEXT FOOD Legacy - Innovative Science & Education for Sustainable Agriculture
Type	Blended Workshop presenting the Deliverables and Tools
Place	Porto Palace Hotel-Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	November 22, 2021
Event aim & purpose	Promotional event at local level under the umbrella of Female Entrepreneurial Week Vol.4// The S.E.G.E. in November 2021 seeks to reinstate for the 4th consecutive time the International Forum of Women's Entrepreneurship Week "Female Entrepreneurial Week", with the aim of bringing together once again the business community in Thessaloniki. Specifically, the event will take place on 22-25 November . This year's Forum aims at innovation and funding by giving participants the opportunity to present all of their operational skills and to exchange experiences and ideas.
Participants	Check Participant List- Approximately 111
Position	The aim of the blended workshop was to present the current achievements and state of art of the NEXT FOOD project combining digital and physical participation of about 57 people locally, 109 views on the live channel link, 54 people participating in the ZOOM link shared.
Expected outreach	We expect to have the maximum possible implication of the stakeholders of this workshop for future use of the methods developed in the project
Results	The NEXT Food legacy workshop planned to present the project results and main achievements and focusing its main interest on the female aspect in agricultural sector, presenting synergies and good practices from Greece.9 presenters have been welcomed during the meeting and 216 people participating live (physically and digitally).

NextFOOD Workshop Greek Translation live video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sVjcpMV4w4Y>

NextFOOD Workshop English Translation live video:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zw9blz-JAhw>

Event title:	NextFOOD (WP2) -Reflecting and planning the Agroecology Course in Kerala
Type	Workshop
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	November 23, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The objective of the Workshop was to do a reflection of the previous course and to plan for the upcoming course.
Relevance to the project	The workshop succeeded in bringing together all stakeholders including students, mentors and facilitators. As a result, a curriculum was set for the course
Type of audience	Audience (Participants) included students, mentors, researchers, teachers
Estimated size of targeted audience	12
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Kerala
Goal of presence	To participate in curriculum development of Short Course on Agroecology: Action Learning and Research and make suggestions for new curriculum development.
Feedback from the audience	The stakeholders contributed towards discussion on how to refine the course. They suggested new educational activities to include in the upcoming course
Stakeholders engaged	Students from the previous course, facilitators

Event title:	Certificate Course on Agroecology: Action Research and Education
Type	One Month Certificate Course
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	25-11-2021 to 22-12-2021
Event aim & purpose	Providing 28-day training for post graduate students to practice competences using 'Next food' model of action learning and enhance action research capability
Relevance to the project	The course act as an experiential learning platform and data generated from the course, including learner and client document, competence assessments are used for research in the project.
Type of audience	Students. Teachers and Farmers
Estimated size of targeted audience	15 (including students, farmers and mentors)
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	University of Kerala WHH
Goal of presence	Centre for Agroecology hosts the course with an aim to popularize action research and education.
Feedback from the audience	The course provided opportunity for students indulge action learning by participating in various educational activities including reflection sessions, field visits, and group activities.
Stakeholders engaged	Students, Facilitators, Mentors, Farmers

3.1.20 December 2021

Type and number of events:

- WP/Partners meeting (2)
- Workshop/Master Course (1)
- Exposure visit (1)
- Peer learning meeting/Digital (1)
- Workshop /Case (1)
- Workshop/Digital (1)

Field	Input
Event title	Meeting between a representative of WP1 and a developer from SLU
Type	Work Meeting (LU is responsible for coordinating the work regarding the development of an online audit tool based on D1.2 – Audit tool for research and education. The meeting was held in this context)
Place	Online
Dates	December 8, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of the event was to discuss the possibility of the online tool being developed internally, by developers at SLU, and to determine next steps.
Relevance to the project	The meeting opens for initiating a process of turning D1.2 into a useful and practical self-assessment tool for educators internationally.

Type of audience	Representative of LU (in the capacity as WP1 partner) and a developer from SLU
Estimated size of targeted audience	2
Geographical scope of event	Sweden
Partner(s) involved	LU, SLU
Goal of presence	The event is an important milestone in the optimization and dissemination of D1.2 in WP1

Field	Input
Event title	Forest management and preservation at the same time – is this possible?
Type	Educational meeting / Workshop Organization
Place	Private forest estate - Sämjesta, Sweden
Dates	December 8, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The course is based on an ecological and biological theme. Focus is on how to manage production forests in a way that benefits economy as well as nature conservation. The course was developed within the Next food project and the learning goals to a great extent depend on what the participants, i.e., learners as well as teachers, wanted to learn and their contributions to the learning process At this meeting, we focused on opportunities with alternative tree species, to think about bogs and ancient monuments and what we can create for value by actively reflecting.
Relevance to the project	WP 2 Case study – develop the model to also work for private individuals and forestry officials who sometimes have limited resources in time and commitment.
Type of audience	Private forest owners who have an interest in alternative methods of forestry. Officials who wish to broaden their knowledge around microhabitats. Researchers who want to learn more about the complex issue of forestry
Estimated size of targeted audience	Participants – 9 forest owners, 2 forestry officials and 3 Skogforsk NextFOOD-team members
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	Education and action research

Feedback from the audience

I find it interesting to walk in an unknown forest, to be aware of what is there, it is easier to take in new information and learn new things when emotions and own previous knowledge do not obscure the view. (learner)
 Glad we had our own time to think and that we did group work! (learner)
 One thing that I thought about and which there is a lot of focus on in society nowadays is a third and important aspect of forestry (both globally and locally) alongside the issue of production versus biodiversity, namely the role of forestry in global warming. I would have liked to have discussed this issue a little more. (learner)

Stakeholders engaged

Private forest owners that are members of a forest owners association in the middle of Sweden and forestry officials working at this organisation

Field	Input
Event title	Sustainability matters - novel tools to transform education and businesses
Type	Online event in collaboration with SDGs Labs
Place	Zoom (online)
Dates	December 13, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The objective of the peer learning meetings is to share experiences between cases and facilitate generation of new knowledge regarding action learning and action research. In this particular meeting, the case representatives discussed multi-actor involvement in the casework and how to implement action learning in an online setting.
Relevance to the project	Dissemination of the NextFOOD project and the Toolbox in particular
Type of audience	This event is aimed at educators and trainers of adults in all fields. It will introduce innovative methods used by European projects and universities to enhance sustainable practice and action
Estimated size of targeted audience	50-100
Geographical scope of event	Global
Partner(s) involved	NMBU and ISEKI
Goal of presence	Dissemination of the project (To encourage use of the <u>SDGs Labs</u> and NextFOOD online tools)

Field	Input
Event title	Master course presentation on sustainable food systems (Strategies in sustainable transition)
Type	Workshop
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	December 8, 20/21
Event aim & purpose	Lecture on the master course for students at 'strategies in sustainable transition'
Relevance to the project	These students are included in the key target group for the project.
Type of audience	Mainly student interested in planning, sustainability, climate, food etc
Estimated size of targeted audience	At this day 7 students participated
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Niels Heine Kristensen, Roskilde University Stine Rosenlund Hansen, RUC
Goal of presence	Teaching research-based knowledge
Feedback from the audience	Very interested audience where lectures were followed by discussions and reflections
Stakeholders engaged	Students

Field	Input
Event title	Meeting of WP5 partners regarding the final deliverable – ready to use peer review system
Type	WP5 Meeting (LU is responsible for coordinating the work regarding the final deliverable. The meeting was held in this context)
Place	Online
Dates	December 9, 2021
Event aim & purpose	The purpose of the event was to gather and review the inputs of the various WP5 partners regarding the final deliverable, start up the analytical process, and to determine next steps.
Relevance to the project	The meeting brings the WP5 partners together to jointly establish the overall structure and content of the final deliverable.
Type of audience	Representatives of the WP5 project partners
Estimated size of targeted audience	8
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	LU, SLU, AFS, USB
Goal of presence	The event is an important milestone in the finalisation of the final deliverable in WP5

Event title:	Exposure visits to Haritha Club, Secretariate, Kerala
Type	Exposure visit
Place	Trivandrum, Kerala, India
Dates	December 19, 2021
Event aim & purpose	To familiarize students with current initiatives towards community supported agriculture
Relevance to the project	It provided an opportunity for students to witness initiatives of Government of Kerala to promote farming in urban areas.
Type of audience	Students and officials
Estimated size of targeted audience	15
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	University of Kerala
Goal of presence	Centre for Agroecology and Public Health, by arranging an exposure visit for students, made first step towards participatory action in community supported agriculture at Haritha Club.
Feedback from the audience	Students used the opportunity to understand contemporary initiatives of Government of Kerala towards greening urban spaces and opportunities for participatory action.
Stakeholders engaged	Students, Facilitators, Government officials

Field	Input
Event title	Enhancement and Certification of PDO and PGI products
Type	Toolkit Workshop
Place	Thessaloniki Greece
Dates	December 21, 2021
Event aim & purpose	ACRCM presented the actions offer promote the PDO and PGI products of the Central Macedonia, and success exemplifications.
Relevance to the project	ACRCM presented the effects of the implementation of European projects in the Reinforcement of the competitiveness and extroversion of SMEs.

Type of audience	Farmers, stockbreeders, owners of processing unit of foods, agriculturists and students.
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	ACRCM
Goal of presence	The event took place in the context of the series of informative events “Toolkit Workshops” organised by the organization “New Agriculture New Generation”. These are flexible and short workshops, which are carried out by renowned scientists and professionals in the field and each time present a business tool, useful for those who work or operate in the agrofood sector.
Feedback from the audience	In accordance with the objectives of NextFOOD project “Educating the Next Generation of Professionals in the AgroFood sector” it was pointed out the need of digital skills and digital literacy among articular professionals.
Stakeholders engaged	https://www.generationag.org/nea/nea/1305-toolkit-workshop-pistopoihsh-kai-anadeiksh-proionton-pop-kai-pge

3.1.21 January 2022

Type and number of events:

- Workshop (1)
- Digital-WP Partners meeting/Cases (4)
- Workshop / Case (1)

Field	Input
	WP2 case workshops
Event title	Final reflection workshops with cases
Type	Reflection workshops
Place	Teams (online)
Dates	19/01/2022 (UoC and UoK); 20/01/2022 (UNISG and NMBU); 25/01/2022 (UCH and SEKEM); 31/01/2022 (ISEKI and Skogforsk); 17/02/2022 (CIHEAM and AFS)

Event aim & purpose	The aim of these reflection workshops was to look back at four years of NextFOOD and for each of the cases to present key advices and prerequisites for implementing action learning based on their experiences, and for the two cases together to discuss ideas for how to overcome their main challenge.
Relevance to the project	Case development and project reflection
Type of audience	Case contributors and facilitators
Estimated size of targeted audience	Approximately 10 (2+ from each case)
Geographical scope of event	N/A
Partner(s) involved	NMBU/WP2 partners
Goal of presence	Case development

WP2 ACTION RESEARCH FACILITATION

Field	Input
Event title	Forest management and preservation at the same time – is this possible?
Type	Educational meeting / Workshop
Place	Private forest estate - Uggeln, Sweden
Dates	January 13, 2022
Event aim & purpose	The course is based on an ecological and biological theme. Focus is on how to manage production forests in a way that benefits economy as well as nature conservation. The course was developed within the Next food project and the learning goals to a great extent depend on what the participants, i.e., learners as well as teachers, wanted to learn and their contributions to the learning process At this meeting, we focused on how to create other values than wood production in your forest and get paid for it. How to value a property and what we learnt during the course
Relevance to the project	WP 2 Case study – develop the model to also work for private individuals and forestry officials who sometimes have limited resources in time and commitment.
Type of audience	Private forest owners who have an interest in alternative methods of forestry. Officials who wish to broaden their knowledge around microhabitats.

	Researchers who want to learn more about the complex issue of forestry
Estimated size of targeted audience	Participants – 9 forest owners, 4 Skogforsk NextFOOD-team members
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	Education and action research
Feedback from the audience	As usual very rewarding and pleasant in a way that makes the job more fun and more insightful. Very good design work for both teachers and students, I would say. More of this type! (teacher) A great day without time pressure and everyone came to speak. Nice summaries. (teacher) I am struck by the fact that the young people in the group seem to have a clear vision of how the company/farm should be run and provide returns as part of the family's livelihood. (learner)
Stakeholders engaged	Private forest owners that are members of a forest owners association in the middle of Sweden and forestry officials working at this organisation

Field	Input
Event title	Thematic Study Day on climate
Type	Workshop
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	January 31, 2022
Event aim & purpose	Full day conference and workshops for students interested in sustainable transition
Relevance to the project	This student is included in the key target group for the project.
Type of audience	Mainly student interested in planning, sustainability, climate, agriculture, food etc
Estimated size of targeted audience	28
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Niels Heine Kristensen, Roskilde University
Goal of presence	Invited speaker
Feedback from the audience	Very positive feedback on presentation with follow up discussions
Stakeholders engaged	Students

3.1.22 February 2022

Type and number of events: (0)

3.1.23 March 2022

Type and number of events:

- Seminar (2)

Field	Input
Event title	START kick-off seminar
Type	Participation in seminar
Place	Sønderborg, Denmark
Dates	March 21, 2022
Event aim & purpose	Explore potential collaboration between Danish researchers in the field of sustainable food systems
Relevance to the project	Presentation of project aim and results
Type of audience	Researchers
Estimated size of targeted audience	70
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Roskilde University
Goal of presence	Project dissemination and feedback
Stakeholders engaged	Researchers

Field	Input
Event title	Food Studies Day
Type	Seminar/Organization of a seminar
Place	Roskilde, Denmark
Dates	March 16, 2022
Event aim & purpose	To introduce study and research collaboration opportunities between students, practitioners and researchers in region Zealand.
Relevance to the project	Dissemination of project aim and results, inputs and network.
Type of audience	Students, practitioners and researchers in region Zealand
Estimated size of targeted audience	35

Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Roskilde University
Goal of presence	Network, feedback
Feedback from the audience	Very positive, new networks was established, inspiration gained.

3.1.24 April 2022

Type and number of events:

- Partner's Conference (1)
- Dissemination event (1)

Partners' Conference

05 – 7 April 2022

Program

Tuesday, 5 April, pre-meeting

09:00-12:30 WP-related meetings

- WP2 case workshop
- Financial and administrative meeting

12:30-14:00 Lunch together at the campus canteen

14:00- 19:00 Study visits at Castle del Monte and the Vineyard Torre Vento

19:00- 22:00 Networking dinner at Vineyard Torre Vento.

Wednesday, 6 April

09:00-10:30 Catch-up workshop –
impact & conclusion for the final report

10:30 -11:00 Coffee and tea

11:00-11:30 Project officer comments on the project (online)

11:30 -12:30 IFA student competition, winning team presentation

12:30-14.00 Lunch together at the hotel

14:00-18:00 Study visit to CIHEAM case study Coastal Park, visit to Ostuni town

19.30-22:00 Welcome dinner at the campus –
presentation and tour of CIHEAM & Bari campus

Thursday, 7 April

9:00-11:00 Presentations of NextFOOD overall research outcomes,
10 min. per work package

11:00-11:30 Coffee & Tea

11:30-13:30 Workshop: NextFOOD roadmap

13:30-15:00 Lunch together at the hotel

15:00-16:00 Wrap-up workshop

16:00-17:00 Executive committee

19:30-22:00 Dinner together at the hotel –
monograph presentation and celebration

All the presentation are available here:

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LhtsAbSiKAQEuKzAm39

Field	Input
Event Title	«NextFOOD Legacy - Enhancing the co-creation of innovation and knowledge in agriculture, forestry and related bio-value chains
Type	Event Presenting the Deliverables and Tools of NextFOOD project
Place	Porto Palace Hotel-Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	April 18, 2022
Event aim & Purpose	Promotional event at local level with the aim of bringing together once again the business community in Thessaloniki.
Name	Blended Workshop on Next Food Legacy
Participants	Approximately 50
Partner (s)	ACRCM

Position	The aim of the blended workshop was to present the current achievements and state of art of the NEXT FOOD project.
Expected outreach	We expect to have the maximum possible implication of the stakeholders of this workshop for future use of the methods developed in the project
	The ACRCM organised its final workshop for the presentation of the Project Deliverables and Tools f in Thessaloniki, Greece on the 18th April 2022, with the title: «NEXT FOOD Legacy - Enhancing the co-creation of innovation and knowledge in agriculture, forestry and related bio-value chains”.
	Mr. <u>Apostolos Tzitzikostas</u> , Governor of the Region Central Macedonia, pointed the importance of NextFOOD project and emphasized the effects of the implementation of its outputs for the Greek agri-food sector.

3.1.25 Upcoming Event: June 2022

Type and number of events:

- Conference (1)

Field	Input
Event title	8th International Conference on Higher Education Advances (HEAd'22)
Type	Conference

	Participation
Place	Valencia, Spain (hybrid conference)
Dates	June 14 – 17, 2022
Event aim & purpose	The conference is a consolidated forum for researchers and practitioners to exchange ideas, experiences, opinions and research results relating to the preparation of students, teaching/learning methodologies and the organization of educational systems.
Relevance to the project	Being an innovative international educational activity, the action-research data that was collected and analysed since the beginning of NextFOOD in 2018, was put together in a paper that was submitted for the conference submission deadline 11 February 2022. It is expected that the paper will be accepted (latest 6 April 2022) and appear in the conference proceedings, published by UPV Press, and will be provided with a DOI number and submitted to be indexed in major international bibliographic databases. Previous editions are indexed in Scopus and the Thomson-Reuters Conference Proceedings Citation Index – Web of Science Core Collection (former ISI Proceedings).
Estimated size of targeted audience	>200 participants
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association
Goal of presence	Paper accepted 6 April 2022. Title: “Core Competences in Agri-food Sustainability: Student Self-Assessment After Online Action-Learning” (by Katherine Flynn, Christoph Knobl and Line Lindner).
	> HEAD'22 June 14-17, 2022 · Valencia, Spain (headconf.org)

3.2 Additional information for events reported in deliverable 6.6 (May 2018 – April 2020)

3.2.1 Event reporting by date with additional information

June 2018

	<i>NOTES: This event was included by mistake</i>
Event title	Agroecology: Action Learning in Farming and Food Systems- Norwegian Case Study-
Type	Workshop
Dates	May – June 2018
Place	Norway
Type of audience	Students, researchers, experts-
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	60
Partner (s) involved	Norwegian University of Life Sciences

September 2018

	<i>NOTES: Typographical errors</i>
Event title	Master Course
Type	Action Learning Seminar 30 ECTS MSc course
Place	Norway
Dates	September 3, 2018
Geographical scope of event	National
Estimate size of target audience	30
Partner(s) involved	Norwegian University of Life Sciences
	The Master course in Agroecology at NMBU. Students get a rich experience of food production by working one full day at a farm in Norway. The ultimate goals of the master's course are to reduce the distance between academia and society and to bridge the all too frequent gap between knowing and doing with regard to complex challenges such as sustainability of agri-food systems.

	<i>NOTES: Typographical errors</i>
Event title	WP1 -Workshop
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting

Place	Budweis, Czech Republic
Dates	September 4, 2018
Estimated size of targeted audience	30 -15
Geographical scope of event	International

October 2018

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	Skogforsk case – introductory meeting
Type	Information
Place	Uppsala, Sweden
Dates	December 7, 2018
Event aim & purpose	Meeting with the team of forestry contractors to introduce the NextFOOD-case and discuss the content.
Relevance to the project	WP 2 case study
Type of audience	Forestry contractors who will participate in the case
Estimated size of targeted audience	10
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Goal of presence	To meet with our “students”
Feedback from the audience	A constructive discussion about the planned case study
Stakeholders engaged	Forestry contractor and Forest company

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	Kick-off workshop ISEKI
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Bologna, Italy
Dates	October 22, 2018
Estimated size of targeted audience	10
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	NMBU, ISEKI

December 2018

	<i>NOTES: Typographical errors and missing information</i>
Event title	The NextFOOD Project: Drawing together a vision
Type	Workshop
Place	Kolkata, India
Dates	December 14-15, 2018

Estimate size of target audience	30 ---20
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	Deutsche Welthungerhilfe- University of Calcutta, NMBU, SLU
	The NextFOOD pedagogy is tried and tested in Kolkata, India under Indo-Norway collaboration programme in education by NextFOOD partner Welthungerhilfe and University of Calcutta. The concluding workshop with students, faculties and guests was during 14th-15th December in Kolkata.

February 2019

	<i>NOTES: Typographical errors and missing information</i>
Event title	Co-design of a future Master Program in Agroecology and Sustainable food systems
Type	Workshop
Place	Pollenzo, Italy
Dates	February 26-27 28 , 2019
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	20 30
Partner(s) involved	University of Gastronomy Science, NMBU, USB, RUC, UNIBO <i>Researchers from the 12 NextFood Cases</i>
	NextFOOD took part in the co-design of a future Master Program in Agroecology and Sustainable food systems. Together with faculty staff and students from the University of Gastronomy Science and representatives from the Slowfood movement, NextFOOD partners discussed the design of a one-year MSc program integrating the action-oriented and learner-centric NextFOOD approach. The new program is an extension of the existing and well-renowned action-learning courses at the UNISG, which have been further developed as one of the cases of NextFOOD. The delegates left Pollenzo with a positive spirit, not at least as a result of the insightful contributions made and the enthusiasm expressed by the UNISG students invited to the workshop.

Gathering key stakeholders in a workshop with the aim of developing an outline of a new master program in agroecology based on the NextFOOD model

March 2019

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	Informal Meetings
Type	Bilateral Meetings
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	March 13-14, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Informal meetings with a large number of stakeholders from public and private sector were also conducted in order to have an overview about the potential interested stakeholders that will be involved in the case. There was developed an interesting approach - it will be developed a website that will facilitate the contact between students, teachers, stakeholders on the following topics : joining on research teams, internships at the students and stakeholders requests, jobs, participating in different events related to agri-food sector - like fairs, conferences, workshops, summer or winter schools and valuable databases with relevant references.
Estimated size of targeted audience	50
Type of audience	High-school students, teachers, students, academic staff, representatives of companies and state institutions
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea
Feedback from the audience	All the persons invited at these events agreed to support the training programme.
Stakeholders engaged	Identification of opportunities and collaborations by setting up the activities in the NextFOOD project.

April 2019

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	Kick-off workshop CIHEAM
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Bari, Italy
Dates	April 2-3, 2019

Event aim & purpose	Gathering key stakeholders to hold a workshop with the aim of developing an action plan for education based on the Next food model
Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Type of audience	Key case stakeholders, WP2 case facilitators, students, researchers
Geographical scope of event	Local
Partner(s) involved	NMBU, CIHEAM

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	Kick-off workshop USB
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	České Budějovice, Czech Republic
Dates	April 24-25, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Gathering key stakeholders to hold a workshop with the aim of developing an action plan for education based on the NextFOOD model
Estimated size of targeted audience	20
Type of audience	Key case stakeholders, WP2 case facilitators, students, researchers
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	NMBU, University of South Bohemia

May 2019

	<i>NOTES: Missing information</i>
Event title	Greek NextFOOD Case
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Thessaloniki, Greece
Dates	May 9-10, 2019
	<i>Launching the casework in the Greek WP2 case</i>
Geographical scope of event	International
Estimate size of target audience	30
Type of audience	<i>Key case stakeholders, WP2 case facilitators, students, teachers, researchers, extension workers</i>
Partners Involved	AFS, NMBU, IHU

September 2019

	<i>NOTES: Missing information</i>
Event title	The NextFOOD approach in the Swedish case
Type	Workshop
Place	Uppsala, Sweden
Dates	September 16-17, 2019
Event aim & purpose	The aim of the workshop was to achieve a shared understanding of the shift that we are aiming for and what it would require to make the shift. One of the outcomes is a plan of implementation – what, who, when and where. <i>Gathering key stakeholders to hold a workshop with the aim of developing an action plan for education based on the NextFOOD model</i>
Relevance to the project	To illustrate the application of the NextFOOD learning-model in a case where the participants are researchers and forestry professionals.
Type of audience	7 Participants. Experts who will participate in the case study and NMBU-team <i>Key case stakeholders, WP2 case facilitators, researchers, institute leadership</i>
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk, NMBU
	Support and discussion with the NMBU-team. A constructive discussion about the learning model and application in the forestry case

October 2019

	<i>NOTES: Missing information</i>
Event title	WP2 - Workshop
Type	Workshop/Partners Meeting
Place	Vienna, Austria
Dates	October 23-25, 2019
Estimated size of targeted audience	30
<i>Partners</i>	<i>NMBU, ISEKI, UNISG, SLU, University of Calcutta, University of Kerala, AFS, University of Oradea, CIHEAM, SKOGFORSK, Mekelle University, SEKEM, RUC</i>
Geographical scope of event	International
	WP2: Action Research in 12 (+1) cases During the workshop the partners had the chance to: a) Increase Knowledge of all of the NextFOOD cases

	<p>b) Had a deeper understanding of what it means to be a learning facilitator</p> <p>c) Become aware of what it means to be an action researcher</p> <p>d) Increase understanding of the potentials of a NextFOOD toolbox</p> <p>e) Exchange ideas as to how the cases can learn from each other and cooperate with other work-packages in the project.</p>
https://youtu.be/Ai3DtrGvAIU	

November 2019

	<i>NOTES: Missing information</i>
Event title	FoodFactory-4-Us Introduction to the Competition
Type	Webinar
Place	Online/ ISEKI-Food Association organised the webinar on GoToWebinar
Dates	November 7, 2019
Estimated size of targeted audience	21 attendees – or more as more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device.
Partners	ISEKI-Food Association
Geographical scope of event	International
Feedback from the audience	Participants were asked to rate on a level of 1-5 (where 5 is most positive and 1 is the most negative) the usefulness of the presentation. The average rate was 4.8. To the question of how engaged the participants were, the average rate was 4.3.
Stakeholders engaged	https://food-sta.eu/ssc2019-b

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	Building relationships around food in high schools and urban arenas
Type	Public meeting
Place	Åas, Norway
Dates	November 22, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Students presented their preliminary case work results and facilitated dialogues with the workshop participants to co-create ideas for future action. At this event, both key stakeholders from the student case work sites, fellow students, faculty and other interested people gathered in a dialogue

	space to work on relevant issues that requires input from multiple parties, which is a manifestation of the NextFOOD model.
Estimated size of targeted audience	50
Type of audience	Urban farmers, school canteen chefs, teachers, municipal representatives, county representatives, students, faculty, researchers
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	NMBU

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	Food Factory-4-Us: Student Presentation Webinar
Type	Webinar
Place	Online
Dates	November 20, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Each team gave a 5- to 10-minute presentation on a practical experience the members have had in the cereals sector e.g., an internship they did, a visit to a company, volunteer activity or a presentation on an aspect of cereals of interest. Number two out of 6 webinars
Estimated size of targeted audience	17 attendees – or more as more than one attendee may be attending in front of the electronic device.
Type of audience	Masters' students
Geographical scope of event	International
Partner(s) involved	ISEKI-Food Association
Feedback from the audience	Participants were asked to rate on a level of 1-5 (where 5 is most positive and 1 is the most negative) the usefulness of the presentation. The average rate was 3,1. To the question of how engaged the participants were, the average rate was 3,3.
Stakeholders engaged	https://food-sta.eu/ssc2019-b

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	Stakeholder meeting
Type	Telephone conference
Place	Uppsala and Sundsvall, Sweden
Dates	November 18, 2019
Event aim & purpose	Information and introduction of the NextFOOD method and case that is a vocational training course for forestry professionals, aiming at higher understanding about logging techniques, strategies, and methods to increase quality and number of micro-habitats in production forests.

Relevance to the project	The meeting includes a new stakeholder from Swedish forestry to the NextFOOD project.
Geographical scope of event	National
Partner(s) involved	Skogforsk
Stakeholders engaged	Representative of a Swedish forest company

December 2019

	<i>NOTES: Not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	"Ecotrophelia" 8th Edition
Type	National student conference
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	1 st -4 th of December 2019
Event aim & purpose	Presentation of case studies on food innovation by students coordinated by academic staff from different Romanian universities.
Relevance to the project	The audience was informed about the activity of the teams within the NextFOOD project. The topics of the group projects have been presented and the state of their development.
Type of audience	Students, academic staff from different universities from Romania.
Estimated size of targeted audience	50 persons – students and teachers
Geographical scope of event	National event
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea, "Stefan cel Mare" University, Suceava, "Dunarea de Jos" University, Galati
Goal of presence	Participation into the contest
Feedback from the audience	The students from other universities have been interested in the work the students from Oradea have undertaken. They were encouraged as for the next competition they could participate with their projects.

	<i>NOTES: The following event was not included in D6.6</i>
Event title	International Conference of Young Scientists Innovativa 2019
Type	International Conference, 9 th Edition
Place	Oradea, Romania
Dates	3 rd – 5 th of December 2019
Event aim & purpose	New trends in foodstuff production and food safety, like using natural extracts, fusion cuisine

	combining of agri-food raw materials by students from Romania and Poland
Relevance to the project	Among the participants there were members of the teams involved in project – both highschool students and university students. The activity of the teams involved in the NextFOOD project has been presented in front of the other participants.
Type of audience	High school students, teachers, university students, academic staff
Estimated size of targeted audience	50 persons
Geographical scope of event	Regional event
Partner(s) involved	University of Oradea, Romania University of <i>Rzeszów</i> , Poland Vocational School from Cadea, Romania “Mihai Viteazul” Vocational School, Romania
Goal of presence	To acquire soft skills, professional skills, due to the presentation of the 6 projects within the NextFOOD project
Feedback from the audience	The project teams were encouraged to continue their work. There were questions and suggestions on the projects.

4 Overview of dissemination and training activities

4.1 Activities undertaken throughout the project lifetime (1st May 2018 – 30th April 2022)

4.1.1 Total number of events

MAY 2018 - APRIL 2022					
TYPE	Number of Events	Number of Participants (approximately)	International	National	1 > Partner (s) Involved
Organization of NextFOOD Conferences	6	476	6	1	2
Consortium conferences	5	273	5	0	5
WP's Partners Meetings	57	692	53	3	56
Organization of a workshop/seminar/networking event	176	4449	50	102	36
Participating/presenting on international/national conference	21	1768	14	6	8
Participating in workshop / seminar / networking event	13	965	10	3	0
TOTAL	278	8623	138	115	107

4.1.2 NextFOOD Conferences

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)	1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Consortium's Conferences							
	1	50	1		02-04/05/18	1	Kick off Meeting, SLU
TOTAL 2018	1	50	1			1	
	1	50	1		27-29/05/19	1	USB / 1st Conference
TOTAL 2019	1	50	1			1	
	1	50	1		3-5/6/20	1	2nd Conference/AFS
TOTAL 2020	1	50	1			1	
	1	80	1		4-25/5/21	1	3rd Conference / SLU
TOTAL 2021	1	80	1			1	
	1	43	1			1	
TOTAL 2022	1	43	1		5-7/4/22	1	Final Conference/CIHEAM
SUBTOTAL	5	273	5	0		5	

4.1.3 Consortium Conferences

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Organization of Conferences/NextFOOD							
	1	43	1		20-21/08/19		UNISG
TOTAL 2019	1	43	1	0		0	
	1	20	1		27/8/2020	1	SLU, NMBU
TOTAL 2020	1	20	1	0		1	
	1	110	1		18/02/21		ISEKI
	1	170	1		23/6-25/6/21		ISEKI
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	89	1		13/12/21	1	NMMU, ISEKI
TOTAL (2021)	3	369	3	0		1	
	1	44	1		27/1/2022		ISEKI
TOTAL (2022)	1	44	1	0		0	
SUBTOTAL	6	476	6	1		2	

4.2 Activities by year

4.2.1 WP Partners Meetings: 1st May 2018 – 31st December 2018

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)	1 > Partner (s) Involved	
WP's Partners Meetings							
	1	15	1		04/09/18	1	USB, SLU
	1	30	1		03/09/18	1	NMBU
	1	40	1		00/09/18	1	NMBU, SLU, UNIOR, USB, AFS, BIOINSTITUT, SKOGFORSK, CIHEAM, WHH, SDF, MEKELLE, IHU, IFA, UNISG
	1	10			22/10/18	1	ISEKI, UNIBO, NMBU
	1	16	1		10-11/09/18	1	UoCALCUTTA-UCHILE-CIHEAM
	1	16	1		10/11/18	1	RUC-LU-SLU-ISEKI-UoCALCUTTA-UCHILE-CIHEAM
TOTAL 2018	6	127	5	0		6	

4.2.2 WP Partners Meetings: 1st January 2019 – 31st December 2019

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)	1 > Partner (s) Involved	
WP's Partners Meetings							
	1	20	1		28-28/02/19	1	UNISG, NMBU, USB, RUC, UNIBO
	1	5	1		28/03/19	1	MEKELE, NMBU
	1	20		1	2-3/4/19	1	CIHEAM/WP2 Partners
	1	20	1		24-25/4/19	1	USB, NMBU
	1	30	1		09/05/19	1	IHU, AFS, NMBU
	1	30	1		23-25/10/19	1	WP2 (ISEKI, NMBU, UNISG, SLU, UoCAL, UoKER, AFS, UNIOR, CIHEAM, SKOGFORSK, MEKELLE, SEKEM, RUC
	1	30	1		9-10/12/2019	1	RUC-LU-SLU-ISEKI-UoCALCUTTA-UCHILE-CIHEAM
TOTAL 2019	7	155	6	1		7	

4.2.3 WP Partners Meetings: 1st January 2020 – 31st December 2020

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
WP's Partners Meetings							
	1	12	1		14-15/01/20	1	ACRCM, BIOINSTITUT, AFS, ISEKI, SLU /WP6
	1	12	1		29/01/20	1	RUC, NMBU, UNIBO, USB, LU, AFS, SLU
	1	14	1		3-5/6/2020	1	ACRCM, MEKELE, BIOINSTITUT, AFS, ISEKI, SLU, WHH, SEKEM, /WP6
	1	16	1		04/06/20	1	RUC-LU-SLU-ISEKI-UoCALCUTTA-UCHILE-CHEAM
	1	6	1		30/06/20	1	ACRCM, MEKELE, BIOINSTITUT, AFS/WP6
	1	15	1		1-3/9/2020	1	SLU
	1	7	1		03/09/20	1	ACRCM, AFS, ISEKI, BIOINSTITUT, AFS/WP6
	1	10			22-23/9/20	1	ACRCM, AFS, ISEKI, BIOINSTITUT, AFS, WHH, MEKELE, SEKEM/WP6
	1	7	1		10/12/20	1	ACRCM, MEKELE, BIOINSTITUT, AFS/WP6
	1	3	1		17/12/20		ISEKI, UCHILE, BIOINSTITUT
					1/7-31/12/20		UNIBO (Total 7 workshops conducted from other partners supporting task 4.2)
TOTAL 2020	10	102	6	0			6

4.2.4 WP Partners Meetings: 1st January 2021 – 31st December 2021

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)	1 > Partner (s) Involved	
WP's Partners Meetings							
	1	15	1	0	18/1/2021	1	SLU, WHH, MEKELE, LUND, UNIBO
	1	8	2	0	4/3/2021	1	AFS, ACRCM, ISEKI, UCHILE, BIOINSTITUTE
	1	20	1	0	4/3/2021	1	CASE LEADERS
	1	15	1	0	9/4/21'	1	WP2 partners
	1	15	1	0	23/6/2021	1	WP2 partners
	1	20	1	0	29/6/2021	1	WP2 partners
	1	5	1	0	29/7/2021	1	NMBU, ACRCM
	1	5	1	0	30/08/21	1	NMBU, ACRCM
	1	3	1	0	15/09/21	1	BIOINSTITUTE, ACRCM
	1	5	0	1	29/09/21	1	LUND, RUC, SLU
	1	15	1	0	13/10/2021	1	WP2 partners
	1	5	1	0	18/10/2021	1	WP2 partners
	1	5	1	0	19/10/2021	1	NMBU, UCH
	1	5	1	0	20/10/2021	1	NMBU, ISEKI

4.2.5 WP Partners Meetings: 1st January 2022 – 30th April 2022

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)	
						1 > Partner (s) Involved
WP's Partners Meetings						
	1	10	1	0	19/01/22	1 NMBU, UoC, UoK
	1	10	1	0	20/01/22	1 UNISG, NMBU
	1	10	1	0	25/01/22	1 NMBU, UCH, SEKEM
	1	10	1	0	31/01/22	1 NMBU, ISEKI, Skogforsk
	1	10	1	0	17/02/22	1 NMBU, CIHEAM, AFS
	1	10	1	0	31/01/22	1 NMBU, ISEKI, Skogforsk
	1	10	1	0	17/02/22	1 NMBU, CIHEAM, AFS
TOTAL2022	7	70	7	0		7
SUBTOTAL- WP's Partners Meetings (2018-2022)	57	692	53	3		56

4.2.6 Workshops/Seminars/Training Sessions/Dissemination Events: 1st May 2018 – 31st December 2018

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Organization of a workshop/seminar/net working event							
	1	30	1		06/06/18		AFS
	1	25		1	01/05/18-01/06/18		UNISG
	1	50		1	11/7/2018		UCHILE
	1	32		1	16/07/18		UNIOR
	1	30		1	03/09/18		NMBU
	1	25		1	10/09/18		AFS
	1	100	1		09/09/18		AFS
	1	5	1		26/10/18		SKOGFORSK
	1	15		1	00/10/18		IHU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	20		1	10/10/2018	1	AFS, LUND
	1	8		1	00/11/18		SLU
	1	48		1	28/11/2018		UNIOR
	1	10		1	3/12/2018		SKOGFORSK
	1	10		1	7/12/2018		SKOGFORSK
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	20	1		14-15/12/18	1	UoCalc, (NMBU, SLU)
	1	35		1	17/12/18		AFS
TOTAL 2018	16	463	4	12		2	

4.2.7 Workshops/Seminars/Training Sessions/Dissemination Events: 1st January 2019 – 31st December 2019

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Organization of a workshop/seminar/net working event/							
	1	25	1		00/01/2019		CIHEAM
	1	15		1	15/02/19		AFS
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	20		1	17/01/19	1	BIOINSTITUTE, USB
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	20		1	19/01/19	1	BIOINSTITUTE
	1	120		1	11/12/19		UNIOR
	1	8		1	11/12/19		RUC
	1	35		1	21/02/19		ACRCM
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	11	1		28/2/2019	1	ISEKI, UNIBO
	1	40	1		1/3/2019		CIHEAM
	1	70		1	13/3/2019		UNISG
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	50		1	13-14/03/19	1	ISEKI, UNIBO
	1	50		1	13-14/3/19		UNIOR
	1	17		1	19/03/19		UoCalc
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	5	1		19/03/19	1	ISEKI, UNIBO
	1	20		1	25/03/19		MEKELE
	1	5	1		26/03/19	1	MEKELE

	1	5	1		26/03/19	1	MEKELE
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	26	1		27-28/3/2019	1	MEKELE, NMBU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	15	1		27/03/19	1	UoKERA SLU, NMBU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	2	128	1		28-29/3/2019	1	UoKER, SLU, NMBU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	8	1		04/04/19	1	ISEKI, UNIBO
	1	50	1		12-14/04/19		ACRCM
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	20	1		2-3/4/19	1	NMBU, CIHEAM
	1	30	1		5/4/2019		UNISG
	1	9	1		16/04/19		ISEKI
	1	12		1	16/04/19		UNIBO
	1	20		1	23/04/19		MEKELE
	1	13		1	29/04/19		UCHILE
	1	20	1		13/05/19		CIHEAM
	1	7		1	14/05/19		RUC
	1	6		1	14/05/19		RUC
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	300		1	19/03/19	1	IHU, AFS, ACRCM
	1	120	1		22/05/19		ACRCM
	1	12		1	16/05/19		UNIBO
	1	12		1	07/08/19		UNIBO
	1	10		1	07/08/19		ACRCM
	1	20		1	06/09/19		RUC
	1	60	1		12-14/06/19	1	AFS, ACRCM
	1	10		1	13/08/19		ACRCM
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	11	1		19/08/19	1	ISEKI, UNIBO
		20	1		21-22/07/19		MEKELE
	1	20		1	00/09/19		AFS
1 > Partner (s) Involved	2	7	1		16-17/9/2019	1	SKOGFORSK, NMBU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	2	30	1		25-29/09/19	1	ACRCM, AFS, IHU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	50		1	15/10/2019	1	BIOINSTITUTE, USB
	1	50		1	19/10/19		UoCalc,
	1	21	1		07/11/19	1	ISEKI
	1	3		1	18/11/19		SKOGFORSK
	1	21	1		07/11/19	1	ISEKI

4.2.8 Workshops/Seminars/Training Sessions/Dissemination Events: 1st January 2020 – 31st December 2020

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Organization of a workshop/seminar/net working event							
	1	6		1	13/01/20		RUC
	1	15	1		17/01/20		ISEKI
	1	5		1	20/01/20		SKOGFORSK
	1	21		1	24/01/20		Focus Group/MEKELE
	1	40	1		24/01/20		UNISG
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	70		1	20/02/20	1	IHU, AFS
	1	5		1	04/02/20		SKOGFORSK
	1	25		1	05/02/20		ACRCM
1 > Partner (s) Involved	2	70	1		22-24/02/20	1	ACRCM , AFS
	1	10		1	28/02/20		MEKELE
	1	61	1		06/03/20		ISEKI
	1	11		1	10/03/20		UoCalc
	1	15		1	10/03/20		RUC
	1	6		1	20/03/20		SKOGFORSK
	1	25		1	1-30/4/20		SLU
	1	10		1	26/05/20		SKOGFORSK
	1	8		1	26/06/20		SKOGFORSK
	1	5		1	22/07/20		SLU
	1	10		1	26/08/20		LUND
	1	10		1	08/09/20		SKOGFORSK
	1	8		1	08/09/20		UoCalc
	1	5		1	21/09/20		LUND
	1	9		1	25/09/20		UoCalc
	1	5		1	24/09/20		UCHILE
	1	8		1	24/09/20		SLU
	1	4		1	28/09/20		SLU
	1	5		1	08/10/20		NMBU

	1	5		1	08/10/20		NMBU
	1	7	1		08/10/20		ISEKI
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	45		1	18-22/10/20	1	AFS, ACRCM
	1	15		1	21/10/20		AFS
	1	10	1		21/10/20		SLU
	1	30			29/10/20		UoKER
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	23		1	12/11/20	1	ACRCM, AFS
	1	8			15/11/20		UoKER
	1	8		1	16/11/20		UoKER
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	10		1	18/11/20	1	SLU, NMBU, RUC
	1	7		1	18/11/20		CIHEAM
	1			1	18/11/20		UNIBO
	1	20	1		18/11-14/12/20		UoKER
	1	10	1		18/11/20-20/11/20		RUC
	1	60		1	20/11/2020		SLU
	1	30		1	14/12/2020		RUC
	1	47		1	21/12/2020		UoCalc
TOTAL 2020	45	808	8	34		5	

4.2.9 Workshops/Seminars/Training Sessions/Dissemination Events: 1st January 2021 – 31st December 2021

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Organization of a workshop/seminar/net working event							
	1	12	1		26/1/2021		SLU
	1	110	1		18/2/2021		ISEKI
	1	20	1	1	23/2/2021		ACRCM
	1	27		1	4/3/2021		ACRCM
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	6	1		4/3/2021	1	BIOINSTITUT, AFS, ACRCM, ISEKI, UCHILE
	1	20		1	8/3/2021		RUC
	1	6	1		11/3/2021		ACRCM
	1	6		1	15/3/2021		RUC
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	5	1		16/3/2021	1	ACRCM, SLU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	4	1		1/4/2021	1	ACRCM, SLU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	6		1	21/5/2021		ACRCM, IHU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	16	1		26/5/2021	1	ACRCM, UNIOR
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	20		1	3/6/2021	1	AFS, IHU
	1	13		1	16/09/21		SKOGFORSK
	5	20		1	10-11/9/21 & 17-19/9/21		SEKEM/Helipolis University

	5	20		1	10-11/9/21 & 17-19/9/21		SEKEM/Helipolis University
	1	13		1	6/10/2021		SKOGFORSK
	3	21		1	15-17/10/21		SEKEM/Helipolis University
	10	61			17/10-28/10/21		SEKEM/Helipolis University
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	300		1	25/10/2021	1	AFS, IHU
	1	7		1	11/11/21		RUC
	1	3		1	17/11/21		RUC
	1	13		1	17/11/21		SKOGFORSK
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	111	1		21/11/2021	1	ACRCM, AFS, IHU
	1	12		1	23/11/21		UoKERALA
	1	15	1		25/11-22/12/21		UoCALCUTTA
	1	7		1	08/12/21		RUC
	1	14		1	08/12/21		SKOGFORSK
	1	15		1	19/12/21		UoKERALA
	1	15		1	21/12/21		UoKERALA
	5	25		1	1/4/20-30/4/21		SLU
TOTAL 2021	49	923	10	20		7	

SUBTOTAL-Organization of a workshop/seminar/networking event/conference (2018-2022)

176

4449

50

102

36

4.2.10 Workshops/Seminars/Training Sessions/Dissemination Events: 1st January 2022 – 30th April 2022

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Organization of a workshop/seminar/net working event							
	1	13		1	13/1/2022		SKOGFORSK
	1	28		1	31/01/22		RUC
	1	35		1	16/03/22		RUC
	1		1		12/04/22		ISEKI
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	50		1	18/4/2022	1	ACRCM
TOTAL 2022	5	126	1	4		1	

SUBTOTAL-Organization of a workshop/seminar/networking event/conference (2018-2022)	176	4449	50	102		36	
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4.2.11 Participation in international/national conferences: 1st May 2018 – 31st December 2018

	Number of Event	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating/presenting on international/national conference							
	1	90	1		9/5/2018		UNIOR
	1	50	1		22-24/5/18		SLU
	1	30	1		05-06/09/18		UNIOR
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	80	1		26-28/09/18	1	AFS, LUND
	1	100	1		17-19/10/18		UCHILE
	1	52		1	10/10-02/11/18		UNIOR
	2	50	1		19-21/10/18		UNIOR
	1	52		1	31/10-2/11/18		UNIOR
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	200	1		01-03/11/18	1	AFS, LUND
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	80	1		22-23/11/18	1	UCHILE, SLU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	35		1	13-15/12/18	1	UNIOR, ISEKI
TOTAL 2018	12	799	8	3		4	

4.2.12 Participation in international/national conferences: 1st January 2019 – 31st December 2019

	Number of Event	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating/presenting on international/national conference							
	1	70		1	13/03/19		UNISG
	1	100		1	05/04/19		ACRCM
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	200	1		00/08/19	1	AFS, LUND
	1	110		1	04-05/07/19		UoCalc
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	100	1		7-9/10/19	1	ISEKI, UNIBO
	1	150	1		28-29/10/19		SLU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	198	1		26-28/09/19	1	UNISG, NMBU
	1	21	1		9-11/10/19		Conference/LUND
TOTAL 2019	8	949	5	3		3	

4.2.13 Participation in international/national conferences: 1st January 2020 – 31st December 2020

	Number of Event	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating/presenting on international/national conference							
	1	20	1		27/8/2020	1	SLU, NMBU
TOTAL 2020	1	20	1	0		1	

4.2.14 Participation in international/national conferences: 1st January 2021 – 31st December 2021

	Number of Event	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating/presenting on international/national conference							
	1	50	1		20/05/21		RUC
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	400			21-23/06/21	1	AFS, SLU
	1	45		1	18/11/21		RUC
TOTAL 2021	1	495	1	1		0	

4.2.15 Participation in international/national conferences: 1st January 2022 – 30th April 2022

	Number of Event	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating/presenting on international/national conference							
	1	200	1		14-17/6/22		ISEKI
TOTAL 2022	1	200	1	0		0	
SUBTOTAL- Participating/presenting on international/national conference (2018-2022)	21	1768	14	6		8	

4.2.16 Participation in Workshops/Seminars/Networking events: 1st May 2018 – 30th April 2018

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating in workshop / seminar / networking event							
	1	70	1		00/6/18		SLU
	1	30	1		28/8-9/7/2018		UNIOR
TOTAL 2018	2	100	2	0		0	

4.2.17 Participation in Workshops/Seminars/Networking events: 1st January 2019 – 31st December 2019

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating in workshop / seminar / networking event							
	1	30	1		04/02/19		ACRCM
	1	5	1		04-08/02/19		UNIOR
	1	30	1		15-17/04/19		SLU
	1	50	1		12/05/19		UNISG
	1	30	1		17-29/06/19		UNIOR
	1	150	1		20/9/2019		UNISG
	1	300		1	11/11/19		ACRCM
TOTAL 2019	7	595	6	1		0	

4.2.18 Participation in Workshops/Seminars/Networking events: 1st January 2020 – 31st December 2021

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating in workshop / seminar / networking event							
TOTAL 2020	0	0	0	0			0
	1	10	1		17/5/2021		ACRCM
	1	80		1	02/06/21		ACRCM
	1	30	1		28/6/2021		SLU
1 > Partner (s) Involved	1	150		1	13/9/2021	1	ACRCM, AFS
TOTAL 2021	4	270	2	2			1

4.2.19 Participation in Workshops/Seminars/Networking events: 1st January 2022 – 30th April 2022

	Number of Events	Number of Participants	International	National	Date (dd/mm/yy)		
						1 > Partner (s) Involved	
Participating in workshop / seminar / networking event							
	1	70		1	21/03/22		RUC
	1		1		12/04/22		ISEKI
TOTAL 2022	2	70	1	1			0
SUBTOTOTAL - Participating in workshop / seminar / networking event (2018-2022)	13	965	10	3		0	